

Baltarusių tėvų asociacija Lietuvoje
Асацыяцыя беларускіх бацькоў у Літве

Association of Belarusian Parents in Lithuania

BELARUSIAN FAMILIES IN LITHUANIA: INTEGRATION AND PRESERVATION OF IDENTITY

An Analysis of Needs, Barriers, and Prospects
Based on a Study by the Association of Belarusian Parents in Lithuania (2025)

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Executive Summary

This study is based on a survey conducted in the summer of 2025 and reflects the situation of the Belarusian family community in Lithuania at a moment of transition from individual adaptation to organized civic engagement. The findings are not intended to be representative of the entire Belarusian population in Lithuania; however, they document the needs, challenges, and priorities of the most active segment of Belarusian families, concentrated primarily in the city of Vilnius and the Vilnius District. This group constitutes an important source of demand for advocacy, dialogue with state institutions, and systemic solutions in the fields of education and integration.

In recent years, Lithuania has experienced a significant transformation in the structure of the Belarusian diaspora, characterized by a growing proportion of families with children. The concentration of these families in the capital region places increasing pressure on social and educational infrastructure. Access to education has emerged as a particularly acute issue, as it must simultaneously support children's integration into Lithuanian society while preserving the Belarusian language and identity.

The existing system is not fully equipped to meet this demand. The only Belarusian-language institution in Lithuania, Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija, operates at the limits of its capacity, while Lithuanian-language institutions often lack sufficient tools and experience to effectively work with migrant children. As a result, a significant number of Belarusian children enroll in Russian-language institutions, a choice that many parents perceive as forced and undesirable.

The study shows that most Belarusian families are in a phase of active adaptation and hold predominantly temporary legal status, which intensifies feelings of instability and creates demand for legal support, advocacy, and social guarantees. At the same time, families' needs are complex and encompass all age groups of children. Many of the challenges related to access to education and integration opportunities are geographically concentrated and are particularly acute in Vilnius.

The language situation deserves particular attention. Most respondents' children use Russian in their daily lives; at the same time, parents demonstrate a clear aspiration for their children to learn Belarusian in order to preserve their identity and Lithuanian in order to achieve successful integration. Russian, however, is not viewed as a desirable long-term option. Parents express dissatisfaction with the quality of Lithuanian language instruction, particularly due to the lack of a systematic approach to teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language and insufficient integration support for migrant children. At the same time, dissatisfaction is expressed both about the absence of opportunities to study Belarusian in most educational institutions and about the use of Russian in the educational process at the only Belarusian-language gymnasium.

Despite a high level of uncertainty, the majority of respondents view Lithuania as their likely country of residence in the near term and as a potential country of permanent residence for their children. The success of integration – primarily through the acquisition of Lithuanian language skills and access to quality education – is a key factor shaping these decisions. An overwhelming majority of parents consider integration into Lithuanian society necessary and are already taking concrete steps in this direction. At the same time, they face significant barriers, including insufficient language proficiency, limited contact with the Lithuanian environment, and restricted access to information and integration programs.

The study identifies a clear demand for institutionalized representation and protection of the interests of Belarusian families in Lithuania, particularly in the field of education. An overwhelming majority of respondents support the idea of establishing an organization that could unite Belarusian families, serve as a channel of communication with state institutions, and contribute to the development of systemic solutions. Key priorities include improving approaches to teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language, strengthening mechanisms for the integration of migrant children, and expanding opportunities for the preservation of the Belarusian language and cultural identity.

Respondents also emphasize the importance of communication with Lithuanian society and public institutions. They seek to articulate their willingness to contribute to Lithuania, to inform Lithuanians about the circumstances faced by Belarusian migrants, and to explain the need for support and proactive measures that would facilitate faster integration of Belarusian families. At the same time, they stress that preserving Belarusian identity in Lithuania does not contradict integration and can contribute to the country's broader social resilience and security.

Overall, the study confirms that the active segment of the Belarusian family community in Lithuania is oriented toward long-term integration and is ready for constructive dialogue. This creates a foundation for effective cooperation with Lithuanian state institutions and civil society organizations, provided there is a timely and systemic response to the needs identified in this study.

The policy recommendations formulated on the basis of this research, and in light of Resolution No. 2499 of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe, are addressed to key actors shaping and implementing policies in the fields of education, integration, and family support in Lithuania. These include national authorities – primarily the Ministry of Education, Science and Sport, the Ministry of Social Security and Labor, the Ministry of Culture, and the Department of National Minorities under the Government of Lithuania – as well as municipal authorities, particularly the Municipality of Vilnius and its education-related units; preschool and school education institutions; civil society organizations working in the fields of education and integration; and other actors involved in public dialogue and communication, including the media.

Part 1. Belarusian Family Migration to Lithuania: Context, Integration Challenges, and Civic Response

1.1. Scale and Dynamics of Migration (2020–2025)

Over the past five years, Lithuania has received a record number of citizens of Belarus. Since 2020, this number has been increasing at a rapid pace. At the beginning of 2020, according to data from the *Migracijos departamentas prie Lietuvos Respublikos vidaus reikalų ministerijos* (Migration Department under the Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Lithuania; hereinafter *Migracijos departamentas*, 2025), 17,769 citizens of Belarus were residing in Lithuania; by the beginning of 2022, this figure had already reached 31,028 (an increase of 74.6%).

The number of Belarusian citizens residing in Lithuania peaked on January 1, 2024, reaching 62,167 individuals (an increase of 100.4% compared to 2022). Thereafter, the figure began to decline and, as of November 1, 2025, stood at 50,895 people, representing a decrease of 18.1% over a period of one year and ten months.

However, this figure does not reflect the actual number of citizens of Belarus who reside permanently in Lithuania. The absolute majority of the 50,895 individuals hold temporary residence permits – 46,753 people as of November 1, 2025. An analysis of this group based on data from the *Migracijos departamentas* makes it possible to identify several categories under which Belarusian citizens are granted temporary residence permits in Lithuania. The most common basis is employment. A total of 21,243 citizens of Belarus hold temporary residence permits on the grounds of work, accounting for 45.4% of all those residing in Lithuania on a temporary residence permit.

At the same time, according to data from the *Užimtumo tarnyba* (Employment Service of Lithuania), the majority of Belarusian citizens living in Lithuania are employed as international freight truck drivers (LRT.lt, 2024). Consequently, a substantial share of Belarusians holding temporary residence permits on the basis of employment are drivers. As a rule, this category does not in fact reside in Lithuania on a permanent basis. The same may apply to other categories of workers who do not relocate to Lithuania but are employed by Lithuanian employers while moving between Belarus and Lithuania.

Thus, the actual number of citizens of Belarus who reside permanently in Lithuania is clearly lower than the total number of temporary residence permit holders. Among them are families with children. Official statistics do not single out this category of migrants separately. At the same time, the experience of adaptation of Belarusian families to a new environment, as well as their integration into Lithuanian society, has its own specific characteristics.

1.2. Family Migration: Estimated Scale and Geographic Concentration

In 2025, the *Lietuvos socialinių mokslų centro Sociologijos institutas* (Institute of Sociology of the Lithuanian Centre for Social Sciences) conducted a study of Belarusian family migration to Lithuania (Shcherbina & Chubrik, 2025), seeking to answer the question of who constitutes this category of migrants, what their integration models are, and what challenges they face. Based on two methodological approaches, the authors concluded that by the end of 2024 the number of citizens of Belarus living in Lithuania as families could amount to approximately 14.6 thousand people, or about 30% of the total number of immigrants from Belarus. The authors also estimate

that the number of Belarusian families may be around 5,000, including approximately 2,800 families with children, raising an estimated 4,205 children.

A significant share of these families is likely concentrated in the city of Vilnius and Vilnius District. According to data from the *Migracijos departamentas* (2025), at the beginning of 2025, out of 174,321 foreign nationals residing in Lithuania, 68,112 (39%) had declared their place of residence in Vilnius and Vilnius District, including 60,842 (34.9%) residing directly in the city of Vilnius. Given Vilnius's proximity to the border with Belarus, as well as the ethno-linguistic context, the share of Belarusians living in Vilnius and its surrounding areas is likely to be even higher.

According to data from the *VĮ Registrų centras* (State Enterprise Centre of Registers, 2025), the total number of individuals who had declared their place of residence in the city and were born in Belarus amounted to 36,709 as of November 4, 2025, including 2,156 individuals under the age of 18. The number of children under the age of five – that is, those who clearly relocated to Lithuania in recent years – stands at 284. Although this group also includes citizens of Lithuania, these figures nevertheless help to illustrate the overall picture.

1.3. Changes in the Demographic Profile and Integration Potential

Thus, while the exact number of Belarusian families and children who have relocated to Lithuania remains a matter of debate, it can be stated that it has increased significantly over the past five years. Belarusians had previously constituted the third largest national minority group in Lithuania, after Poles and Russians; however, recent migration has likely altered not only their overall numbers but also their age structure. According to the 2021 Population Census of Lithuania (*Lietuvos statistikos departamentas* – Statistics Lithuania, 2021), Belarusians accounted for approximately 1% of the total population (28.2 thousand). The largest shares were found in the age groups of 60-69 years (2.1% of all residents in this age group), over 80 years (1.8%), 70-79 years (1.6%), and 50-59 years (1.4%). These figures also include citizens of Lithuania who identify themselves as belonging to the Belarusian nationality.

Based on the results of the study on family migration to Lithuania (Shcherbina & Chubrik, 2025), an additional 12,013 to 14,773 family migrants can be added to this number as of the end of 2024. This category is likely composed primarily of individuals of working age as well as minors. As a result, Lithuania has seen the arrival of a large number of families with children – something that had not previously been observed in the country. The substantial increase in the size of the national group as a whole and the emergence of a large cohort of Belarusians of working age, including families with children, have created a new context that was not previously characteristic of the Belarusian diaspora in Lithuania.

Belarusian families began to face challenges and questions related to adaptation to a new environment, the resolution of which required the search for appropriate approaches. Shcherbina and Chubrik (2025) note that family migrants, especially families with children, often demonstrate stronger motivation to integrate compared to individual migrants. At the same time, family integration models are typically far more complex and unfold across multiple levels, which can facilitate faster integration. Families with children show a significantly higher interest in information about how the host society functions and have a more pronounced need for opportunities for long-term planning and predictability.

1.4. Key Challenges Faced by Belarusian Families

Among the key challenges faced by Belarusian migrant families in Lithuania, Shcherbina and Chubrik (2025) identify the following:

1. **Lack of security and certainty** (changes in policies toward Belarusians, negative information circulating in the public domain, and a lack of transparency and predictability in decisions made by state institutions);
2. **Legalization challenges** (the absence of clear roadmaps for obtaining permanent residence permits and citizenship, as well as lengthy bureaucratic procedures);
3. **Lack of access to consular services** (the inability to renew passports outside Belarus, among other issues);
4. **Language barriers** (limited access to the labor market, difficulties in accessing education, and challenges in acquiring the Lithuanian language);
5. **Children's education** (the absence of integration programs in schools, insufficient support for learning Lithuanian, and experiences of discrimination).

Thus, alongside the need to address issues typical for most Belarusian immigrants, such as maintaining emotional resilience, resolving legalization and passport-related matters, and dealing with other legal challenges, in short, learning how to navigate a new environment, Belarusian families with children also face the necessity of addressing challenges specific to this group. In addition to ensuring access to quality education for their children, a portion of Belarusian families are concerned with preserving their national identity and securing opportunities for education in their native language while simultaneously integrating into Lithuanian society.

1.5. Demand for Integration Through Bilingual Education and Related Barriers

These families expressed a strong desire to integrate into Lithuanian society not through linguistic assimilation, but by ensuring that their children have the opportunity to study in both Belarusian and Lithuanian. Parents predominantly viewed this bilingual educational model as the optimal path for preserving culture while achieving full integration.

In 2023, an informal initiative of Belarusian parents in Vilnius launched a community-led survey to assess demand for Belarusian-language education options in Lithuania. The survey was conducted between July and October 2023. Its key finding was that families were often forced to choose Russian-language schools when their children were not admitted to *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*, the only Belarusian-language school in Lithuania and the only one of its kind outside Belarus.

At the same time, enrollment in Lithuanian-language schools was not viewed by parents as an ideal alternative, as, in their view, Lithuania lacks a comprehensive support system for newly arrived migrant children. As a result, families who wished their children to study in Lithuanian and Belarusian, rather than Russian, were sometimes left without viable options.

1.6. Civic Response: Activities of the Parents' Initiative

Following the survey, the parents' initiative group undertook a series of actions aimed at addressing the identified problems (*Belarusian Schools in Vilnius. Information Point, 2024*). Initially, their efforts focused on expanding existing educational opportunities by collecting 1,000 signatures in support of opening a second Belarusian-language school in Vilnius, citing the acute shortage of available places at *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*. Lists of prospective students and teachers were compiled.

The initiative actively engaged with local authorities: a meeting was held with the then Vice Mayor of Vilnius, during which the collected signatures and a formal request were submitted. Representatives of the parents also held discussions with *Vilniaus miesto savivaldybė* (Municipality of the City of Vilnius) regarding the possible addition of extra classes at *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*, as well as the potential opening of additional Belarusian-language preschool groups. Given the physical limitations of the existing school building, alternative premises in Vilnius that could accommodate Belarusian-language classes or preschool groups were also discussed. In addition, meetings were organized with politicians and municipal officials in Vilnius and Vilnius District to further examine the situation.

1.7. Outcomes of the Initiative's Activities and Transition to Institutionalization

The informal parents' initiative continued its activities throughout the 2024-2025 academic year, maintaining active contact with the administration of *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*, the *Vilniaus miesto savivaldybė* (Municipality of the City of Vilnius), and other relevant stakeholders.

Despite sustained efforts and evident demand, including 50 rejected applications for the 2024-2025 academic year (*Belarusian Schools in Vilnius. Information Point, 2024*), 34 of which were for primary school students, no new Belarusian-language classes were established, either at *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija* or in other public schools. Municipal authorities acknowledged the situation but considered the establishment of a second Belarusian school to be impractical. As a compromise, they proposed creating new Belarusian-language classes within other schools; however, these plans ultimately were not implemented.

The result of sustained pressure from the community was a limited but positive change – the addition of one extra fifth-grade class at *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija* for the 2025–2026 academic year. However, this modest improvement coincided with a significant loss: the closure of the Belarusian-language kindergarten that had operated alongside the gymnasium (*Nasha Niva, 2025*). As of mid-2025, there were no Belarusian-language kindergartens remaining in Vilnius, or in Lithuania.

Moreover, the underlying structural problem remained unresolved. During the admissions cycle for the 2025-2026 academic year, applications from dozens of Belarusian children were once again rejected, while the overall number of applications declined. It is likely that many families, discouraged by repeated mass rejections, lost confidence in the institution's ability to ensure access to education in their children's native language.

At the same time, *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija* is indeed operating at the limits of its design capacity. While 235 students were enrolled at the gymnasium in the 2019-2020 academic year, this number increased to 381 in 2022-2023 (*Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija, 2023*), and reached 401 students as of September 1, 2024 (*Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*,

2025). Thus, since 2020, student enrollment has grown by 70.6%. Overcrowding and limited physical space significantly constrain the institution's ability to admit new students.

1.8. The Establishment of the Association of Belarusian Parents in Lithuania as a Response to Systemic Challenges

Under these conditions, a group of parents redirected their efforts toward establishing a formal legal entity. In late spring 2025, a new and more detailed survey was launched to collect up-to-date data on the needs of Belarusian families. The survey confirmed the conclusions drawn in 2023:

1. **Demand for bilingual education and integration into Lithuanian society:** there is a clear and high level of demand among parents for Belarusian-language education for their children combined with in-depth learning of the Lithuanian language and integration into Lithuanian society.
2. **Limited availability of existing resources:** the capacity of Belarusian-language education currently available in Lithuania, represented by *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*, is extremely limited (overcrowding, lack of available places, and the closure of preschool groups), making it impossible to meet existing demand. Other institutions do not offer opportunities to study Belarusian, while weekend extracurricular classes are also insufficient to address the demand.
3. **The need to improve the functioning of *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*:** there are specific concerns related to the operation of the gymnasium itself, including inconsistent use of the Belarusian language in the educational process, which require separate discussion within the Belarusian community and targeted solutions to ensure the quality of Belarusian-language education.
4. **Barriers within Lithuanian-language institutions:** parents encounter significant difficulties when attempting to enroll their children in Lithuanian-language institutions, as there is no effective, state-level system for migrant integration and comprehensive support, including adaptation to a new linguistic environment.

The survey also articulated the need for an organization that would represent parents' interests and focus on addressing these and other identified problems and issues. A total of 97.9% of respondents expressed support for the creation of a formal parents' structure, and in August 2025 the Association of Belarusian Parents in Lithuania (*Baltarusių tėvų asociacija Lietuvoje*, 2025) was established. Its emergence was the result of two years of sustained civic engagement. At the same time, while the Association is a clear outcome of this process, it is not a direct institutional successor to the informal parents' initiative.

The following sections are devoted to an analysis of the responses from the 2025 survey and to the development of proposals aimed at addressing the identified challenges.

Conclusions

Thus, based on an analysis of official statistics and the results of previous sociological studies, it can be stated that over the past five years a new social context has emerged in Lithuania, shaped by a record influx of citizens of Belarus. While 17,769 citizens of Belarus were residing in Lithuania at the beginning of 2020, by the end of 2025 this number had risen to 50,895 (an increase of

186%), indicating an unprecedented scale of migration that has also altered the age structure of the Belarusian diaspora.

Unlike earlier waves of migration, the current wave is characterized by a substantial share of families who have relocated with children. According to the study by Shcherbina and Chubrik (2025), family migrants account for around 30% of the total number of Belarusian immigrants, which may correspond to approximately 2,800 families raising more than 4,200 children in Lithuania. A significant proportion of this group is concentrated in the city of Vilnius and Vilnius District, placing considerable pressure on the capital's social infrastructure. Belarusian families face challenges typical for migrants (legalization, legal issues, language barriers), but they also encounter specific tasks related to ensuring access to education and preserving their children's national identity. Family migrants generally demonstrate stronger and more rapid motivation for integration, which takes place across multiple levels.

A key aspect of integration for many parents has become the issue of education in their children's native language alongside integration into Lithuanian society. Some parents view a bilingual model (Belarusian and Lithuanian) as the optimal path toward full integration and cultural preservation, opposing linguistic assimilation and the forced choice of Russian-language schools. Despite the evident demand for Belarusian-language education, the existing education system has been unable to meet this need. The only institution, *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija*, operates at the limits of its design capacity (with student enrollment increasing by 70.6% since 2020), which has resulted in mass rejections during admissions and the closure of the Belarusian-language kindergarten affiliated with the gymnasium in 2025.

In response to these structural challenges, an initiative group of parents has engaged in active advocacy efforts since 2023, including collecting signatures in support of expanding Belarusian-language education, conducting negotiations with the authorities of the city of Vilnius, and searching for alternative premises. Despite limited successes (such as the addition of an extra fifth-grade class at *Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija* in 2025), the structural problems persisted. The culmination of this sustained civic engagement was the establishment of the Association of Belarusian Parents in Lithuania in August 2025, created to provide systematic representation and protection of the interests of Belarusian families.

Thus, this study, based on a survey conducted in the summer of 2025, is carried out at a critical moment when the Belarusian family community has transitioned from individual adaptation to institutionalized civic engagement, making an analysis of their needs and priorities particularly timely.

Part 2. Analysis of the Needs and Challenges of Belarusian Families in Lithuania Based on the Results of the 2025 Survey

2.1. Research Methodology and Characteristics of Respondents

The survey, conducted between June and July 2025, involved 91 respondents. Participation was open to Belarusians who have children and reside permanently in Lithuania. The call for participation was disseminated through the social media channels of projects and initiatives working with Belarusians in Lithuania. Invitations were also shared personally within the Belarusian diaspora in Lithuania.

The survey was anonymous; however, respondents had the option to voluntarily provide their contact details. Overall, 40 respondents chose to do so. As a result, the survey can be considered partially de-anonymized, allowing for the verification of a portion of the respondent pool.

The survey instrument included a set of questions designed to collect both quantitative data (closed-ended questions with predefined answer options) and qualitative information (open-ended questions allowing respondents to provide their own responses).

The questions covered the following thematic blocks:

- **Socio-demographic characteristics:** length and location of residence, legal status, and family composition.
- **Educational trajectories:** children's current place of study, satisfaction with the quality of education, and willingness to change educational institutions.
- **Linguistic landscape:** learning and use of Belarusian, Lithuanian, and other languages.
- **Integration and future plans:** migration intentions and barriers to integration.
- **Demand for advocacy:** the need for institutionalization and the identification of priority areas of activity.

Study Limitations and Interpretation of Results

When interpreting the results of this survey, it is necessary to take into account methodological limitations related to the sampling strategy and data collection.

The survey was conducted using a voluntary response (self-selection sampling) method and was distributed through targeted communication channels, including social media and Belarusian communities and projects operating in Lithuania. As a result, the obtained sample of 91 respondents is targeted but statistically non-representative of the entire population of Belarusians living in Lithuania with children. This means that the survey findings cannot be directly extrapolated to the whole Belarusian population in Lithuania.

The method of distributing the survey through Belarusian initiatives and projects naturally attracted primarily those individuals who:

- **Are active in civic life:** demonstrate a high level of awareness of issues related to education and integration and are motivated to address them;
- **Are well integrated into the Belarusian community:** are aware of the existence of civil society organizations or follow their activities;
- **Have a strong “Belarusian identity”:** are more interested in issues related to the preservation of the Belarusian language and culture.

The fact that 40 out of 91 respondents voluntarily provided their contact details for further participation in the establishment of a parents’ association indicates a high level of interest in civic engagement and advocacy within this subgroup.

Scope of Application of the Findings

Despite its statistical non-representativeness, this survey makes it possible to:

- **Document the challenges of the “active core”:** clearly identify the range and severity of educational, linguistic, and integration-related difficulties faced by the most active and motivated segment of the Belarusian community in Lithuania;
- **Articulate advocacy needs:** the data obtained provide a solid basis for formulating policy recommendations and substantiating the need for organized advocacy efforts;
- **Identify support priorities:** the survey results serve as a roadmap for civil society and state institutions seeking to provide support to Belarusians in Lithuania.

Thus, this study constitutes a **case study** focused on the needs and challenges of the active segment of the Belarusian family diaspora in Lithuania.

Respondent Profile: Geography, Legal Status, and Length of Residence

A total of 91 respondents participated in the survey, each responding on behalf of their family. According to the data obtained, 83 of these families are two-parent households. In total, the surveyed families are raising 151 children, which allows the overall number of individuals covered by the survey to be estimated at no fewer than 327 people residing in Lithuania.

Length of Residence

According to the responses, the distribution of length of residence is as follows:

- **4 families** have been living in Lithuania for **less than one year**;
- **19 families** for **one to two years**;
- **59 families** for **three to four years**;
- **4 families** for **five to six years**;
- **5 families** have been living in Lithuania for **more than seven years**.

Thus, **90% of the families have been living in Lithuania for no more than four years**, while **25% have resided in the country for less than two years**. It can therefore be stated that the majority of respondents are at an early stage of adaptation to the new social and educational environment.

Geographic Distribution

Almost all respondents reside in Vilnius. Only two families live in Klaipėda and one in Kaunas. This indicates a clear concentration of Belarusian families in the capital, which affects both the scale and the nature of the challenges they face.

Legal Status

- **Temporary residence permit in Lithuania:** 75 respondents;
- **Permanent residence permit:** 13 respondents;
- **Other legal grounds:** 3 respondents.

Thus, **82.4%** of study participants reside in Lithuania on the basis of a temporary residence permit, while **14.2%** have a permanent legal status. One respondent holds Lithuanian citizenship, and two others are citizens of other EU member states. At the same time, **96.7%** of all respondents are citizens of Belarus.

The fact that the number of respondents who have been living in Lithuania for less than five years exceeds the number of those holding temporary residence permits can likely be explained, at least in part, by the refugee status held by some respondents.

Age Structure of Children

In total, respondents are raising **151 children**. The age distribution is as follows:

- **Preschool age (under 7 years):** 49 children;
- **Primary school age (7–11 years):** 52 children;
- **Secondary school age (12–19 years):** 50 children.

The largest numbers of children fall within the following age groups (only the five largest groups are listed):

- **Ages 5 and 8:** 15 children each;
- **Age 9:** 12 children;
- **Age 15:** 11 children;
- **Ages 3, 4, 10, and 12:** 9 children each;
- **Ages 11, 14, and 16:** 8 children each.

Conclusions

Thus, the vast majority of Belarusian families who participated in the survey (90%) arrived in Lithuania within the past four years. This indicates that the community is in a phase of active formation and adaptation rather than constituting a long-established ethnic minority. The overwhelming majority of families (over 82%) reside in Lithuania on the basis of temporary residence permits. The absence of permanent resident status or citizenship may create a sense of instability among parents and increase demand for legal support and rights-based advocacy, particularly with regard to legalization procedures and access to social guarantees.

The relatively even distribution of children across all age groups (approximately 50 children in each of the preschool, primary school, and secondary school categories) indicates that the demand for educational and related services is comprehensive in nature. This is not a temporary

spike in a single age group, but rather a sustained need for education at all levels, from preschool to upper secondary education. Challenges related to access to educational, integration, and other opportunities have a clearly localized character and are primarily an issue of the city of Vilnius, where the vast majority of respondents are concentrated.

2.2. The Current Educational Situation: Levels of Satisfaction, Key Challenges, and Possible Solutions

Educational Institutions

A total of **137 children** of the respondents who participated in the survey attend at least **41 educational institutions** in Lithuania, including **14 preschool institutions**, as well as several unspecified institutions (where respondents indicated only the language of instruction). Of these institutions, **39 are located in Vilnius, one in Klaipėda, and one in Kaunas**.

The undisputed leader is **Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**, which is also the **only educational institution in Lithuania with Belarusian as the language of instruction**. It is attended by **45 children from 28 families**. It should be noted that until the 2025–2026 academic year, the gymnasium also offered preschool groups. Thus, of the 45 children, at least **six attended preschool** (some respondents did not specify the educational level of their children).

The second most common choice is the private **Stembridge School**, with predominantly Russian as the language of instruction (the institution’s website declares a Russian–English bilingual model only at the primary school level), attended by **10 children from 7 families**. The third most popular institution is **Vilniaus Naujamesčio mokykla**, with Russian as the language of instruction and **8 students from 6 families**. This is followed by **Vilniaus Levo Karsavino mokykla**, also Russian-language, with **7 students from 5 families**, and **Vilniaus Ateities mokykla**, attended by **6 students from 6 different families**.

Overall, the distribution across institutions can be summarized as follows:

Table 1. Distribution of Students Across Educational Institutions in Lithuania

Institution	Number of students	Language of instruction
Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija	45	Belarusian
Privati mokykla Stembridge	10	Russian
Vilniaus Naujamesčio mokykla	8	Russian
Vilniaus Levo Karsavino mokykla	7	Russian
Unknown kindergardens	7	Russian
Vilniaus Ateities mokykla	6	Russian
Unknown kindergardens	4	Lithuanian
Unknown schools	4	Russian
Erudito Licejus	3	Lithuanian, English
Klaipėdos tarptautinė mokykla UNIVERSA VIA	2	Lithuanian
Mokykla Gravitas Schola	2	Ukrainian
VGTU inžinerijos licėjus	2	Lithuanian
Vilniaus Santaros gimnazija	2	Russian
Vilniaus Aleksandro Puškino gimnazija	2	Russian
Vilniaus darželis-mokykla Svaja	2	Russian
Vilniaus Lazdynų mokykla	2	Russian
Vilniaus Naujininkų progimnazija	2	Lithuanian
Vilniaus Sofijos Kovalevskajos Progimnazija	2	Russian
Kurpaitė kindergarden	2	Russian

Zylutė kindergarden	2	Russian
Kauno Tarptautinė Gimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Klaipėdos Liudviko Stulpino progimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Klaipėdos Simono Dacho progimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Royal Russell mokykla	1	English
Turgelių Aistuvos Gimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Vilniaus Montessori mokykla	1	English
Vilniaus Simono Stanevičiaus progimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Vilniaus Spindulio progimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Vilniaus Vytauto Didžiojo gimnazija	1	English
Vilniaus Žemynos progimnazija	1	Lithuanian
Aitvaras kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Lašelis kindergarden	1	Russian
Mazasis Trinapolis kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Ramunele kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Rytas kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Strazdelis kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Vaivorykštė kindergarden	1	Russian
Verinelis kindergarden	1	Russian
Žiedas kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Zirmunieliai kindergarden	1	Lithuanian
Delfinukas kindergarden	1	Lithuanian

Languages of Instruction

The majority of children are educated in **Russian**, totaling **59 students**, including **16 children at the preschool level**. The second-largest group consists of children educated in **Belarusian – 45 students, six of whom attend preschool groups**. It should be noted that these figures fully correspond to the number of students at **Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**, as it is the only institution in Lithuania offering education in Belarusian.

The third-largest group comprises children educated in **Lithuanian**, numbering **28 students**, including **12 attending preschool institutions**. A small number of respondents indicated **English** as the language of instruction, most often referring to mixed or blended forms of education. In addition, **two students are educated in Ukrainian** at *Gravitas mokykla*.

Table 2. Languages of Instruction and Number of Students

Languages of Instruction		including:	
		School level	Preschool level
Russian	59	43	16
Belarusian	45	39	6
Lithuanian	28	16	12
English	6	5	1
Ukrainian	2	2	0

Satisfaction with Educational Institutions and Reasons for Dissatisfaction

In response to the question about the level of satisfaction with their children's current educational institutions on a scale from 1 to 5, the majority of parents selected a score of **4 (42 respondents)**, indicating a relatively high level of satisfaction. An additional **18 respondents** reported being fully satisfied with the institutions their children attend (score of **5**). A substantial number of respondents rated their satisfaction at **3 (25 respondents)**, suggesting a moderate level of satisfaction or, possibly, the absence of a clearly defined position on this issue. Low satisfaction ratings (**1 and 2**) were reported in only **six cases**, pointing to the existence of a very small group of parents with pronounced dissatisfaction.

Among these responses, **two** concerned **Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**. Single cases of dissatisfaction were reported with **Vilniaus Naujamiesčio mokykla**, **Vilniaus Ateities mokykla**, **VGTU inžinerijos licėjus**, as well as with one unspecified preschool institution.

The results indicate that parents generally evaluate the educational institutions their children attend quite positively: ratings of **4 and 5 prevail (66% of responses)**, reflecting overall satisfaction. At the same time, a substantial share of respondents selected the mid-range option (**3 points, 28% of responses**), pointing to the presence of problems or uncertainties that prevent full satisfaction. Negative ratings, although accounting for only about **6%** of all responses, relate to several different institutions with varying languages of instruction (Belarusian, Russian, and Lithuanian). This suggests the existence of broader systemic issues rather than isolated problems limited to a single institution.

Figure 1. Parents' Level of Satisfaction with Educational Institutions

At the same time, **69 respondents (75.8%)** answered the follow-up question, *“If you are not satisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with?”* (respondents could select one or several of the proposed options or add their own response). Thus, reasons for dissatisfaction with current educational institutions were provided not only by those who are generally dissatisfied, but also by respondents who reported overall satisfaction.

The largest number of respondents selected the option **“lack of Belarusian language instruction”** – **31 respondents**, or **34%**. The second most common response (**29 respondents, or 31.8%**) was dissatisfaction with the **quality of Lithuanian language instruction**. A further

25.3% of respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the **overall quality of subject teaching**, while **22%** pointed to the **lack of support for migrant children**.

The fifth most frequently selected option was **“quality of Belarusian language instruction,”** chosen by **16 respondents (17.6%)**. It should be noted that, taken together, dissatisfaction related to the Belarusian language – either due to its absence or inadequate quality of instruction – was expressed by up to **47 respondents (51.6%)**, representing an absolute majority of responses.

Figure 2. Reasons for Parents’ Dissatisfaction with Their Children’s Educational Institutions

At the same time, in response to the follow-up question, *“Would you like your child(ren) to attend a different educational institution in Lithuania?”*, **28 respondents (30.8%)** expressed a clear willingness to move to another institution (responses 4 and 5). **Forty-three families (47.3%)** selected scores of 2 (**23 respondents**) or 1 (**20 respondents**), indicating that they do not wish their children to study at a different institution. The number of respondents who chose the **mid-range option** was **20 people (22%)**. Thus, approximately **one third of respondents** are clearly prepared to consider transferring their children to another educational institution.

Figure 3. Parents’ Desire to Change Their Children’s Current Educational Institution

An analysis of the educational institutions attended by children of parents who expressed a clear desire to change schools shows that the following institutions were mentioned: **Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija** by **6 respondents**, **Vilniaus Naujamiesčio mokykla** by **5 respondents**, **Vilniaus Ateities mokykla** by **3 respondents**, and **Vilniaus Levo Karsavino mokykla** by **2 respondents**. Single mentions were recorded for **Klaipėdos tarptautinė mokykla UNIVERSA VIA**, **Privati mokykla STEMBRIDGE**, **VG TU inžinerijos licėjus**, and **Vilniaus Aleksandro Puškino gimnazija**.

While no robust conclusions can be drawn with regard to the latter group due to their very limited representation in the survey, several observations can be made concerning the first four institutions.

In the case of **Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**, the six respondents who expressed a clear intention to leave the institution represent **21.4%** of the **28 families** included in the survey whose children attend this gymnasium. This indicates that, although a certain proportion of parents report a high level of dissatisfaction with the gymnasium, the majority of families (**78.6%**) do not, overall, intend to transfer their children to other institutions. The relatively high absolute number of respondents from this gymnasium who expressed a desire to change institutions can largely be explained by the fact that this gymnasium is the most heavily represented institution in the survey sample.

At the same time, a comparatively high level of intention to change educational institutions can be observed among parents whose children attend **Vilniaus Naujamiesčio mokykla** (5 out of 6 respondents, or **83%** of all respondents from this institution), **Vilniaus Ateities mokykla** (3 out of 6, or **50%**), and **Vilniaus Levo Karsavino mokykla** (2 out of 5, or **40%**). It should be noted that these Russian-language institutions rank **third, fourth, and fifth**, respectively, in terms of the number of respondents' children enrolled in them.

As a separate question, respondents were asked to indicate the specific institution to which they would like to transfer their children, as well as the language of instruction they would prefer if the current situation does not meet their needs. An analysis of the responses reveals several key trends.

1. Belarusian-language education at Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija

Out of the **42 respondents** who provided answers to the question about an “ideal” educational institution for their children, **ten (23.8%)** in one way or another indicated that they would like their children to attend the only gymnasium in Lithuania with Belarusian as the language of instruction. Almost all of these respondents currently have children enrolled in Russian-language schools, and only **one family** expressed a desire to transfer to the Skorinos gymnasium from a Lithuanian-language school. Notably, the majority of these respondents indicated that their children do not attend the gymnasium because they were unable to gain admission:

“Skorinos gimnazija – there were no places at first, and later my son no longer wanted to transfer.” (Respondent 12, Russian-language school)

“We have been applying to the Skorinos gimnazija for several years now. There are no places. What is needed is an institution with an adequate attitude from teachers, Belarusian-language instruction, and proper teaching of Lithuanian (not ‘you don’t really need it anyway,’ followed by a failing grade).” (Respondent 24, Russian-language school)

“I want to transfer my son from Levo Karsavino mokykla to Skorinos gimnazija. There were no places there last year.” (Respondent 40, two children in a Belarusian-language school, one child in a Russian-language school)

“Possibly to a Belarusian-language school, but it is difficult to get in.” (Respondent 48, Russian-language school)

“Skorinos gimnazija, but there are not enough places.” (Respondent 79, Russian-language school)

“Skorinos gimnazija - there are no places.” (Respondent 90, Russian-language school)

It should also be noted that some respondents stated that they have **no alternative options** for their children to study in Belarusian and attend Skorinos gimnazija simply because no other such options exist.

“Unfortunately, there are no other educational institutions with Belarusian as the language of instruction.” (Respondent 21, Belarusian-language school)

“...there is no such institution, which is why we study at the gymnasium.” (Respondent 27, Belarusian-language school)

2. Education in Belarusian and Lithuanian

Another notable trend is the presence of a **general demand for education in Belarusian** (without a mandatory link to Skorinos gimnazija) combined with **strong instruction in Lithuanian**. Some respondents also note that such an institution currently does not exist in Lithuania, pointing to the use of Russian and the insufficient quality of Lithuanian language instruction.

“Such an institution does not exist yet :) One with strong Lithuanian and Belarusian instruction, but without the use of Russian.” (Respondent 3, Lithuanian-language school and preschool)

“Either a Belarusian-language school with modern educational approaches, or a Lithuanian one, but the child does not yet have sufficient proficiency in the language.” (Respondent 38, Russian-language preschool)

“Either a Lithuanian or a Belarusian–Lithuanian gymnasium, but there are no places.” (Respondent 87, Russian-language school and preschool)

Some respondents also mentioned the need for a **Belarusian-language preschool**.

“We would like a good Belarusian kindergarten.” (Respondent 15, child aged 5, institution not specified)

“A Belarusian-language kindergarten with English and Lithuanian as additional languages.” (Respondent 74, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

3. Education in Lithuanian

A segment of parents (10 families) expressed a desire for their children to study with Lithuanian as the primary language of instruction. At the same time, several respondents noted that they have not pursued this option due to the language barrier.

“In a Lithuanian school near our home, but the children’s level of Lithuanian is not very high.” (Respondent 34, Russian-language school)

“...we would like to get into a school with Lithuanian as the language of instruction, but we are afraid of the difficulties of a fully Lithuanian-speaking environment.”
(Respondent 36, Russian-language school and kindergarten)

“We would like our children to study in a Lithuanian school, but at the moment they do not have a sufficient level of Lithuanian language proficiency.”
(Respondent 80, Belarusian-language school)

One respondent described an unsuccessful attempt to attend a Lithuanian-language kindergarten, followed by a transfer to a Russian-language kindergarten and later to a school.

“We attended two Lithuanian kindergartens before Stembridge, but the language barrier hindered adaptation, so we decided to transfer to a Russian-language kindergarten.”
(Respondent 46, Russian-language kindergarten)

Among other responses, respondents mentioned interest in English-language education and private schools, while simultaneously noting the lack of sufficient financial resources to pursue such options.

“An English-language educational institution with instruction in Belarusian and Lithuanian, but the lack of sufficient funds prevents us from paying for private school tuition.”
(Respondent 26, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

“Some kind of English-language school, but we have no money.”
(Respondent 50, Russian-language kindergarten)

“We would try the British school, but it is too expensive.”
(Respondent 78, Russian-language school; Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

Respondents’ views on the preferred language of instruction for their children are also reflected in answers to a separate question asking whether they would like their children to study in a different language than their current language of instruction. The responses were distributed as follows:

- “Yes” - 33 responses
- “Difficult to say” - 37 responses
- “No” - 21 responses

Among those who answered this question affirmatively, 21 respondents have children currently studying in Russian, 7 in Belarusian, and 5 in Lithuanian.

At the same time, respondents whose children attend Russian-language schools most frequently mentioned Belarusian (13 respondents), Lithuanian (12 respondents), and English (8 respondents) among their preferred languages of instruction. Respondents were able to indicate multiple preferred languages. Common combinations included Belarusian and Lithuanian (5 respondents), Belarusian and English (3 respondents), and Lithuanian and English (2 respondents). Some respondents indicated only a single preferred language – Belarusian (4 respondents), Lithuanian (4 respondents), or English (2 respondents). One respondent indicated all three of these languages.

Among those who clearly stated that they did not wish to change the language of instruction – that is, those who are fully satisfied with the current situation – 11 respondents have children studying in Belarusian, 4 in Lithuanian, 4 in Russian, and 1 each in English and Ukrainian.

It should also be noted that, regardless of how respondents answered the question about their willingness to change the language of instruction, **not a single one of the 91 respondents identified Russian as a desired language of instruction.**

Education-Related Challenges and Required Support

“What education-related problems have you encountered or are you currently encountering in Lithuania with regard to your children?”. The responses received can be grouped into several main categories.

1. Problems Related to the Lithuanian Language

At least **26 respondents (28.6%)** in one way or another pointed to difficulties related to learning the Lithuanian language. These included both the general complexity of acquiring the language and the absence of a structured system for teaching Lithuanian as a non-native language in educational institutions, an insufficient number of instructional hours, and an unsatisfactory level of teacher professionalism.

“...we would like solid Lithuanian instruction, which the school does not currently provide.”
(Respondent 3, Lithuanian-language school)

“The teaching of Lithuanian in Russian-language schools is at a low level.”
(Respondent 4, Russian-language school)

“Lack of support in learning Lithuanian.”
(Respondent 8, Belarusian-language school)

“...a shortage of textbooks and teachers, and a formal approach to teaching Lithuanian while at the same time requiring proficiency in it.” (Respondent 16, Russian-language school)

“Poor Lithuanian: subject teachers do not explain complex topics, don’t explain much in Lithuanian, while textbooks and workbooks are only in Lithuanian.”
(Respondent 24, Russian-language school)

“More hours are added, but even after two years of six hours per week, the child still cannot speak Lithuanian at even a basic level.”
(Respondent 62, Russian-language school)

“There is not enough Lithuanian, and the teaching methods do not facilitate learning Lithuanian.” (Respondent 75, Russian-language school)

“Teaching Lithuanian as if it were a native language.” (Respondent 85, Russian-language school)

“A heavy workload in Lithuanian at school, but no results after two years. The administration refuses to change the program, referring to the Ministry of Education. As a result, the children do not know Lithuanian.” (Respondent 90, Russian-language school)

Notably, dissatisfaction with the teaching of Lithuanian as one of the main educational problems was most often mentioned by parents whose children attend **Russian-language schools**.

A separate issue was raised regarding the learning of Lithuanian by Belarusian children who arrived in Lithuania within the past few years and are studying in **upper grades**. This group faces **particular difficulties in passing Lithuanian-language examinations** and obtaining a secondary school certificate.

“My older daughter studied for two years at the Russian-language Lithuanian school “Juventos”. Now she is facing graduation exams, and the first major one is Lithuanian, which she did not have time to master. This is very difficult for children. We do not know what we will do if she does not receive a secondary school completion certificate.” (Respondent 63, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

2. Problems Related to the Belarusian Language

Another group of responses concerns the **Belarusian language**. At least **15 respondents (16.5%)** in one way or another pointed to problems related to access to education in Belarusian or difficulties in learning it. Notably, a significant number of respondents also mentioned the Lithuanian language in their responses. Thus, parents’ concern for the Belarusian language is combined with an understanding of the importance of Lithuanian as well.

“Preserving Belarusian. We want children not only to speak it, but also to write and read in Belarusian. We also want solid Lithuanian instruction, which the school does not currently provide.” (Respondent 3, Lithuanian-language school)

“We want Belarusian-language education with active learning of Lithuanian and English.” (Respondent 15)

“There is too little Belarusian. And what is labeled as Belarusian is not always Belarusian in essence.” (Respondent 52, Belarusian-language school)

“Absence of the Belarusian language.” (Respondent 74, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

Some responses specifically addressed **access to Belarusian-language education**, pointing to a lack of institutions and learning opportunities.

“Lack of educational institutions with Belarusian as the language of instruction; difficulties in learning Lithuanian.” (Respondent 11, Russian-language school)

“Lack of Belarusian-language extracurricular classes in educational institutions.”

(Respondent 26, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

“There is no proper Belarusian school. We do not know what is better for the future: trying a Lithuanian gymnasium or switching to English.” *(Respondent 37, Russian-language school)*

“There are too few Belarusian schools.” *(Respondent 61, Russian-language kindergarten)*

“The impossibility of education in Belarusian, poor adaptation of the Lithuanian language curriculum, a low overall quality of education, and too many Russian-language classes.”

(Respondent 87, Russian-language school)

Some respondents also pointed to the **inability to enroll in the only Belarusian-language institution in Lithuania**, as well as dissatisfaction with certain aspects of the educational process there.

“When we relocated, we were forced to enroll in a Russian-language school because there were no places at the Belarusian-language school.”

(Respondent 36, Russian-language school and kindergarten)

“We were unable to get into the primary school at the Skorinos Gymnasium. In the Skorinos kindergarten, the language was almost entirely Russian...”

(Respondent 40, Belarusian- and Russian-language schools)

“The impossibility of enrolling in a gymnasium with Belarusian as the language of instruction.” *(Respondent 65, Russian-language school)*

“It was difficult to get into the Belarusian gymnasium.”

(Respondent 9, Belarusian-language school)

“I would like Russian not to be used at the Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija.”

(Respondent 5, Belarusian-language school)

“The only option for four-year-old children in Vilnius is the kindergarten attached to Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija, but according to feedback from other parents, both in the kindergarten and the school the main language is Russian, and the approach to child upbringing and education is Soviet-style.” *(Respondent 86, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)*

It should be recalled that the survey was conducted in the summer of 2025. As noted above, as of September 2025, the kindergarten attached to the Skorinos gymnasium ceased to operate. The need for a Belarusian-language preschool was also highlighted by other respondents:

“We do not know whether we will be able to find a suitable Belarusian kindergarten.”

(Respondent 32, child under one year old)

3. Problems Related to the Integration of Migrant Children into the Education System

Some responses pointed to the lack of preparedness of the education system – both **formal and non-formal** – to work with migrant children.

“It is almost impossible for migrants to get into a good educational institution...”
(Respondent 4, Russian-language school)

“There is no systemic integration.” (Respondent 6, Russian-language school)

“Extracurricular activities are either in Russian or exclusively in Lithuanian. We would like to see bilingual clubs or ones that help with integration.”
(Respondent 18, Russian-language school)

“After-school education is expensive or only in Lithuanian, which psychologically frightens the child and becomes a barrier to participation.”
(Respondent 25, Russian-language school)

“The education system as a whole is poorly prepared for migrants.”
(Respondent 89, Belarusian-language school)

“There is a lack of understanding that these children have experienced trauma, and that it is much harder for them to study because not only the school is new, but also the approaches, the language, and even their parents have changed due to the stress they have experienced.” (Respondent 31, Lithuanian-language school)

4. General Problems of the Education System

Some respondents also pointed to additional difficulties they encounter that can be attributed to issues affecting the education system as a whole – or at least the institutions attended by respondents’ children – and are not unique to Belarusian families. These include the following:

- Shortage of textbooks

Notably, the majority of such comments came from parents whose children attend **Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**, which may be linked to a shortage of **Belarusian-language textbooks** in particular.

“...quite often there is a lack of textbooks, and instruction depends on electronic textbooks on ‘Eduka’.” (Respondent 24, Russian-language school)

“Some textbooks are missing.” (Respondent 41, Belarusian-language school)

“There are not enough textbooks, and I am dissatisfied with the system for teaching Lithuanian.” (Respondent 41, Belarusian-language school)

“There is a complete lack of textbooks; there are not enough for all students.”
(Respondent 76, Belarusian-language school)

- Inclusion and children with special needs

“...there are almost no qualified specialists to work with children with developmental disabilities.” (Respondent 4, Russian-language school)

“Lack of real inclusion, shortage of textbooks and teachers...”
(Respondent 16, Russian-language school)

“Lack of clear integration pathways for a child with special needs.”

(Respondent 29, Belarusian-language school)

“...there is no support for children with developmental disabilities.”

(Respondent 40, Belarusian-language school)

Among other issues faced by parents, respondents also mentioned a **low level of teacher motivation and qualifications, high staff turnover, overloaded school curricula following the latest education reform, and the problem of bullying in schools.**

For the sake of balance, it should also be noted that some respondents expressed **full satisfaction** with the education system and their personal experience.

“As far as my children are concerned, I am very satisfied with education in Lithuania. My children received support in adapting, they had additional Lithuanian classes, but I am saddened by the fact that most Belarusian children I know attend Russian-language schools.” (Respondent 23, Lithuanian-language school in Klaipeda)

“Everything is completely fine.” (Respondent 79, Russian-language school)

“We did not encounter any particular problems.”

(Respondent 33, Belarusian-language school)

Required Support in the Field of Education

Based on the identified challenges and issues faced by Belarusian families in the field of education, respondents also outlined the types of support that could be beneficial to them in their answers to a corresponding question. The groups of responses are presented below in order of frequency.

1. Support for Learning the Lithuanian Language

At least **28 families (30.8%)** mentioned the need for additional support in learning **Lithuanian as a foreign language**, both for children and for their parents. This applies to **formal education** – including curricula and examination requirements – as well as to **non-formal learning**, such as supplementary classes and opportunities for interaction with native speakers and Lithuanian educational institutions.

“Help communicate to the Ministry of Education that children in national minority schools need a different Lithuanian-language program (at least for primary school students: because with five hours per week over four years, it is possible to fully learn the language, pass the exam, and from grade five study in Lithuanian at the same level as Lithuanian-speaking children).” (Respondent 90, Russian-language school)

“If only there were systematic Lithuanian-language instruction from scratch at school.”

(Respondent 8, Belarusian-language school)

“Organizing educational activities for teachers working with migrant children. Developing and implementing effective methodologies for teaching Lithuanian. Creating spaces for supplementary education for migrant children (clubs, extracurricular groups such as chess, football, board games).” (Respondent 70, Belarusian-language school)

“Additional Lithuanian classes and joint activities with Lithuanian institutions.”

(Respondent 9, Belarusian-language school)

“Develop and use methods for teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language.”

(Respondent 85, Russian-language school)

“Support classes at school where Lithuanian would be taught as a foreign language, so that children could practice dialogues using examples and learn words and expressions.”

(Respondent 78, Russian-language school)

“It would be useful for me personally to improve my Lithuanian in order to be able to freely resolve necessary issues with city authorities or educational institutions.”

(Respondent 23, Lithuanian-language school)

“So that migrant children could take exams at the level required for foreigners.”

(Respondent 48, Russian-language school)

2. Support for Integration into the Lithuanian-Language Educational Environment

A number of responses relate to another topic closely linked to the issue of learning Lithuanian: **at least 10 families** expressed a need for measures aimed at the **integration of Belarusian families into Lithuanian society**.

“Support from the municipality in the effective integration of Belarusian children.”

(Respondent 3, Lithuanian-language school and kindergarten)

“Integration into the Lithuanian-speaking environment. As for the quality of local schools, I don’t know what can be done – that is a broader systemic issue.”

(Respondent 10, Russian- and Belarusian-language schools)

“Organization of Lithuanian-language conversation clubs for children, integration groups into the Lithuanian-speaking environment.”

(Respondent 36, Russian-language school and preschool)

“There probably needs to be some kind of integration program – teaching Lithuanian at an entry level, but for older children.”

(Respondent 80, Belarusian-language school)

“Information support and special adaptation classes in Lithuanian schools.”

(Respondent 87, Russian-language school and kindergarten)

3. Support for Learning the Belarusian Language and Preserving Identity

Survey participants also expressed strong concern about the **learning of the Belarusian language and the preservation of their children’s identity**. Their proposals regarding what should be done in this area can be grouped into a separate category. Respondents pointed to the need to **expand opportunities for preschool and school education in Belarusian**, as well as to **improve the quality of existing Belarusian-language education**. In addition, parents emphasized the importance of enabling children to study **Belarusian language, literature, and history as academic subjects**.

“High-quality, modern opportunities to preserve Belarusian, and the creation of a truly Belarusian (Belarusian-language) environment for children. Belarusian-Lithuanian-English summer camps. Support from the municipality for the effective integration of Belarusian children.” (Respondent 3, Lithuanian-language school and kindergarten)

“The opportunity for a child to be educated in their native language, along with additional Lithuanian language courses for children.” (Respondent 4, Russian-language school)

“We would like a Belarusian preschool and school (Belarusian not just in name, but truly providing quality education), as well as children’s language courses and more creative extracurricular activities.” (Respondent 15, educational institution not specified)

“Create elective classes for learning the Belarusian language, Belarusian literature, the history of Belarus, and Belarusian art.” (Respondent 26, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

“I would like the Belarusian gymnasium to become truly Belarusian.”
(Respondent 27, Belarusian-language school)

“Opening a Belarusian kindergarten.” (Respondent 32, child under one year old)

“Having more than one (non-private) modern school with the possibility to study the Belarusian language.” (Respondent 38, Russian-language kindergarten)

“Belarusian language included in the curriculum.” (Respondent 69, Russian-language school)

“Changes at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija (greater emphasis on Lithuanian and Belarusian; a shift toward more interactive, humanistic, individualized, and democratic educational approaches).” (Respondent 86, Lithuanian-language kindergarten)

4. Other Types of Additional Support

Respondents also mentioned several other types of support they consider necessary. For example, they pointed to the need for **tutors** who could help children integrate into Lithuanian-language educational environments, as well as stronger **support from school administrations** (with some noting that such support was lacking). In addition, parents expressed interest in **consultations regarding their rights**, opportunities to **change educational institutions**, **admission to higher education**, and assistance in **guiding their children’s future educational and career pathways**. Respondents also highlighted the need for access to **psychological support**, including services for children experiencing **post-traumatic stress**, as well as support for children with **additional needs**.

Conclusions

The study covered **137 children** of respondents who attend **at least 41 educational institutions in Lithuania**, almost all of them located in **Vilnius**. The majority (**59 children**) receive education in **Russian**, including a significant number at the preschool level. The **second most common language of instruction is Belarusian: 45 children** study in Belarusian, and all of them are enrolled in the **only Belarusian-language school in Lithuania, Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**. The **third group**, consisting of **28 children**, studies in **Lithuanian**, with **42.9%** of them attending preschool institutions. This distribution indicates a strong concentration of the

Belarusian community around a single Belarusian-language institution, as well as a significant dependence on the Russian-language education sector. At the same time, there is a fairly clear tendency among parents to enroll children in **Lithuanian-language kindergartens**.

Overall satisfaction with educational institutions is relatively high: **66% of parents are satisfied or fully satisfied** with current conditions. However, a more detailed analysis of the reasons for dissatisfaction reveals a number of **structural problems**. An **absolute majority of respondents (51.6%)** expressed dissatisfaction related to the **Belarusian-language factor** – either due to its **complete absence** from the educational process (**34%**) or due to the **insufficient quality of instruction (17.6%)**, including in the only Belarusian-language gymnasium. At the same time, **31.8%** of respondents are dissatisfied with the **quality of Lithuanian-language instruction**, and **22%** point to the **lack of support for migrant children**. This contrast highlights a paradoxical situation: parents are generally satisfied with current educational arrangements, yet at the same time acutely feel the lack of support both for **preserving Belarusian identity** and for **successful integration into Lithuanian society**.

Approximately **one third of respondents (30.8%)** are clearly ready to consider transferring their children to another educational institution. This intention is most pronounced among parents whose children attend **Russian-language schools**. Importantly, **not a single one of the 91 respondents identified Russian as a desirable alternative language of instruction**. Those who wish to change the language of instruction most often named **Belarusian (13 respondents)** or **Lithuanian (12 respondents)**. This points to a strong aspiration toward integration combined with a desire to preserve Belarusian identity, alongside a clear rejection of a Russian-language educational trajectory. A large number of parents expressed a desire to enroll their children in the **Skorinos gymnasium**, while simultaneously noting that they have **no real alternative** for receiving education in Belarusian combined with the study of Lithuanian.

Among the key challenges identified through open-ended questions, the most prominent are **difficulties in learning Lithuanian (28.6%)**, primarily due to the absence of a systematic approach to teaching Lithuanian as a non-native language and an insufficient number of instructional hours. Some parents also pointed to the **lack of preparedness of the education system to work with migrants**. Particular attention was drawn to the difficulties faced by **upper-secondary students**, who struggle to pass state examinations due to an insufficient level of Lithuanian.

Meanwhile, **16.5%** of respondents reported problems related to **access to education in Belarusian** or difficulties in learning it. Respondents mentioned the shortage of Belarusian-language institutions and the inability to enroll in the only Belarusian-language school, **Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**. A number of parents whose children attend this gymnasium voiced criticisms of the institution itself, with the main concern being the **use of Russian in the educational process**. At the same time, parents whose children attend other schools expressed frustration over the **lack of opportunities to study Belarusian** there. Respondents also drew attention to the **recent closure of the only Belarusian-language kindergarten in Vilnius**. Other issues mentioned include a **shortage of textbooks**, shortcomings in working with **children with special needs**, a **low level of teacher motivation and qualifications**, an **overloaded school curriculum**, and the problem of **bullying** in schools.

These challenges directly inform the types of support that respondents consider necessary. **30.8%** reported a need for **additional support in learning Lithuanian as a foreign language**, both for children and for parents themselves. Suggested measures include improving methodologies for teaching Lithuanian to migrants, systematically teaching the language “from

scratch” in schools (including for adolescents), and organizing additional Lithuanian classes with native speakers. Another frequently mentioned need – closely related to the above – is **support for integration into the Lithuanian-language environment**, including the development of integration strategies at the municipal level, the organization of integration-oriented extracurricular activities, and the introduction of tutors in Lithuanian-language institutions.

Parents also emphasized the importance of **learning Belarusian and preserving children’s identity**. Respondents pointed to the need to expand opportunities for **preschool and school education in Belarusian** and to improve the quality of existing Belarusian-language education. Parents whose children attend Lithuanian- and Russian-language schools expressed interest in enabling their children to study **Belarusian language, literature, and history as subjects**. Other forms of support mentioned include **legal consultations**, assistance with **career guidance and admission to higher education**, access to **psychological services** (including for children experiencing post-traumatic stress), and support for **children with special needs**.

2.3. Linguistic Profile of Children and Language Learning

Belarusian Language Proficiency and Learning

Respondents were asked to answer the question: “**Do your children speak Belarusian in everyday life (in the family, with friends, etc.)?**” Participants could select one of the proposed options or provide their own response. The following answer choices were offered:

- Yes, Belarusian is the only and primary language of communication
- Yes, they predominantly use Belarusian (the absolute majority of the time)
- They use Belarusian regularly, but it is not the primary language
- They use Belarusian rarely (the absolute majority of the time another language is used)
- They know Belarusian to some extent but never use it
- They do not know Belarusian

The results indicate that for the children of **78% of respondents (71 responses)**, Belarusian is **not the primary language of communication**. Among them, **26 respondents (28.6% of the total sample)** reported that their children use Belarusian **regularly**, though not most of the time. Others stated that their children use the language **rarely (23 responses, 25.3%)**, **know it but do not use it (15 responses, 16.5%)**, or **do not know it at all (7 responses, 7.7%)**.

Children of **15.4% of respondents (14 responses)** use Belarusian **exclusively or predominantly**. Another **five respondents** indicated that their children speak Belarusian at home but use another language (Lithuanian or Russian) at school, preschool, or with relatives. One respondent reported that their child communicates using a **mixture of three languages** (Belarusian, Lithuanian, and Polish). In these cases, it is difficult to determine whether Belarusian can be considered the dominant language of communication. Depending on interpretation, these responses could reasonably be classified either among children who use Belarusian predominantly or among those who use it regularly. Under the latter approach, the share of children who use Belarusian regularly would increase to **22%**. Thus, even under a broader interpretation, the proportion of respondents whose children are predominantly Belarusian-speaking **does not exceed this level**.

Figure 4. Belarusian Language Proficiency and Usage

At the same time, the children of **51% of respondents** study Belarusian **systematically**. Notably, this share exceeds the percentage of respondents whose children are enrolled in **Pranciškaus**

Skorinos gimnazija (30.8%). This suggests that parents actively seek opportunities for their children to learn Belarusian even when there is no possibility of receiving formal education in the language. Such efforts include participation in extracurricular activities, home-based learning, and language use within Belarusian-speaking families.

Figure 5. Learning of the Belarusian Language

With regard to parental satisfaction with the **teaching of the Belarusian language**, it can be observed that an **absolute majority of respondents are satisfied**. Among those whose children study Belarusian, **61%** reported being **fully satisfied** or **rather satisfied** (13 and 18 responses, respectively).

Another **14 respondents (27%)** indicated a **moderate level of satisfaction** or expressed no clear opinion. The proportion of respondents who are **clearly dissatisfied** with the quality of Belarusian-language instruction amounts to **12%** (four respondents were rather dissatisfied, and two were completely dissatisfied).

Figure 6. Satisfaction with Belarusian Language Instruction

Thus, the majority of parents are satisfied with the overall quality of Belarusian-language instruction. Respondents who had specific concerns provided additional comments in response to the question: **“If you are dissatisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with?”**

Unsurprisingly, most of the criticism relates to **Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija**, the only institution in Vilnius, and Lithuania as a whole, where Belarusian can be studied systematically. The predominant theme in these comments concerns the **use of Russian by teachers during the educational process**. Respondents also raised concerns about the **shortage of textbooks**.

“The quality of instruction.”

(Respondent 5, rating “3”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Belarusian does not dominate at the gymnasium.”

(Respondent 14, rating “3”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Instruction is effectively conducted in Russian.”

(Respondent 19, rating “3”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Communication at the gymnasium takes place in Russian.”

(Respondent 20, rating “2”; one child at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Our language club is very enjoyable, but the children lack grammar.”

(Respondent 24, rating “3”; two children at Vilniaus Levo Karsavino mokykla; Belarusian studied in a Sunday club)

“In the Belarusian gymnasium, instruction should be provided equally in Lithuanian and Belarusian, but instead teaching takes place in Lithuanian and Russian. I am dissatisfied with these approaches. Ninety percent of teachers do not know Belarusian and speak Russian. This is the only Belarusian gymnasium, yet it lacks the most essential element.”

(Respondent 27, rating “2”; one child at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“There is too little Belarusian. We would like more, and more systematic instruction. For now, this depends on our own efforts and extracurricular activities.”

(Respondent 37, rating “4”; one child at Stembriže private school)

“I wish more teachers at Skorinos gimnazija spoke Belarusian.”

(Respondent 40, rating “4”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Even at the Belarusian gymnasium there is a dominance of Russian. It is easier for educators to switch to Russian with Russian-speaking children than to teach them Belarusian.” *(Respondent 52, rating “2”; one child at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)*

“Teachers do not teach children to speak the language; it feels artificial.”

(Respondent 56, rating “2”; one child at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Lack of textbooks.” *(Respondent 67, rating “4”; one child at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)*

“I am dissatisfied with the teaching methods (they are very outdated; teachers appear overworked and of advanced age).”

(Respondent 70, rating “4”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Lack of textbooks and literature in general.”

(Respondent 76, rating “3”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“Some teachers do not have sufficient proficiency in Belarusian and do not encourage children to speak Belarusian.”

(Respondent 80, rating “4”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

“I would like the classes to be held more frequently (currently once per week).”

(Respondent 86, rating “4”; one child at a Lithuanian-language kindergarten; Belarusian studied in a club)

“Regarding Skorinos gimnazija – at the school level, part of the instruction takes place in Russian. At the preschool level, Belarusian was entirely absent.”

(Respondent 89, rating “3”; two children at Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija)

Lithuanian Language Proficiency and Learning

The question regarding the **level of Lithuanian language proficiency** reveals the following pattern. A clear majority of respondents reported that their children have **basic, upper-basic, or lower levels of proficiency**. Altogether, such responses account for **72.5%** of the sample.

Among them, **23 respondents (25.3%)** indicated that their children have a **basic or upper-basic level** of Lithuanian. Another **36 respondents (39.6%)** reported that their children know only **individual words or phrases**, while **7 respondents (7.7%)** stated that their children **do not know Lithuanian at all**.

15 respondents (16.5%) believe that their children have an **intermediate level** of Lithuanian proficiency. The children of **10 respondents (11%)** speak Lithuanian **fluently or almost fluently**.

Figure 7. Lithuanian Language Proficiency

An **absolute majority of respondents (86.8%)** state that their children study Lithuanian **systematically**. Specifically, **70.3% (64 responses)** reported that Lithuanian is studied as a **mandatory subject** at an educational institution, while **16.5% (15 respondents)** indicated that Lithuanian is the **primary language of instruction**. An additional **seven respondents** mentioned that their children study Lithuanian through **supplementary classes**. Only **five respondents (5.5%)** stated that their children **do not study Lithuanian at all**.

Figure 8. Learning of the Lithuanian Language.

With regard to parental satisfaction with the **teaching of Lithuanian**, the situation appears more mixed. **48%** of respondents are **fully satisfied or rather satisfied** (20 and 21 responses, respectively). Another **24 respondents (28%)** report a **moderate level of satisfaction** or are uncertain. At the same time, **24%** of respondents are **rather dissatisfied or completely dissatisfied** with their experience (13 and 8 responses, respectively).

Figure 9. Satisfaction with Lithuanian Language Instruction

Parents were also asked to specify what exactly they find unsatisfactory in the teaching of Lithuanian. Four responses were received from parents whose children study in Lithuanian as the main language of instruction. Overall, they noted that they did not receive additional institutional support in learning Lithuanian and had to make independent efforts to bring their children’s proficiency to an adequate level.

“There was no systematic support from the school or the education department in learning Lithuanian; additional classes took place at our expense and on our own initiative.”

(Respondent 3)

“The child was not taught the language; she learned it independently.” (Respondent 43)

The main group of respondents who provided comments on this question have children attending minority schools with Belarusian or Russian as the language of instruction. Several key patterns can be identified in their responses.

A significant group of respondents (**15 responses**) expressed dissatisfaction with the **methodologies used to teach Lithuanian** to their children. In particular, they pointed to the absence of effective approaches for teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language, as well as the lack of a systematic framework for integrating migrant children into the educational process.

“There is no approach tailored to children for whom Lithuanian is not a native language.”
(Respondent 16, Russian-language school)

“We were dissatisfied with the absence of an integration process: the child was simply placed in a foreign-language environment, did not understand anything, and was not understood.” (Respondent 46, child transferred from a Lithuanian-language kindergarten to a Russian-language one)

“The program is oriented only toward native speakers; there is no adaptation for national minorities.” (Respondent 62, Russian-language school)

“There are no good methodologies for migrant children, the textbooks are ‘boring,’ and there are issues with the assessment system.” (Respondent 70, Belarusian-language school)

“The language is taught as if for native speakers; some topics are difficult to understand.”
(Respondent 79, Russian-language school)

A number of respondents also pointed to the lack of sufficient opportunities for practical language use:

“Textbooks are not adapted for immigrants. There is little speaking practice.”
(Respondent 4, Russian-language school)

“There is a lack of motivation and live practice.” (Respondent 14, Belarusian-language school)

“Too little conversational practice.” (Respondent 36, Russian-language school)

Among other factors, respondents also mentioned **teachers’ attitudes toward their subject**, as well as an **insufficient number of Lithuanian language classes** in educational institutions. Additionally, concerns were raised about the **lack of teacher preparedness to work with children with special needs**.

Russian Language Proficiency and Learning

The linguistic situation regarding children’s **Russian language proficiency** appears as follows. An absolute majority of children possess and use Russian to some extent. Only **5.5% of respondents (5 responses)** indicated that their children **do not know Russian at all**. Another **12%** reported that their children know Russian but **almost never (2.2%) or rarely (9.9%) use it**. A further **14.3%** stated that their children use Russian **regularly**, though it is not their primary language of communication. The majority of children either **predominantly use Russian (56%, 51 responses)** or **speak it exclusively (12.1%, 11 responses)**. Thus, **68.1%** of respondents report that Russian is the **predominant language of communication** for their children.

Figure 10. Russian Language Proficiency

At the same time, **more than half of the children (55%) do not study Russian systematically.**

Figure 11. Learning of the Russian Language.

Parents whose children study Russian were also asked about their satisfaction with its instruction. The majority of them (**62%**) expressed satisfaction, **28%** selected the middle option, and **10%** reported being dissatisfied.

Figure 12. Satisfaction with Russian language Instruction

At the same time, one notable difference can be observed in responses regarding dissatisfaction with the teaching of Russian compared to similar questions about other languages. Only **seven comments** were received, and just one of them referred to specific shortcomings in the instructional process; this response came from a family whose children study in Belarusian (Respondent 76). One respondent indicated that they would like their children to study Russian systematically (Belarusian-language school, Respondent 21).

The remaining comments reflect a generally critical attitude toward the study of Russian, including from respondents whose children attend Russian-language institutions:

“I believe it would be better if instruction were conducted in Belarusian.”
(Respondent 25, Russian-language school)

“I do not want my child to be taught the language of the occupiers.”
(Respondent 27, Belarusian-language school)

“Too many hours per week; it would be better to add more Lithuanian.”
(Respondent 34, Russian-language school)

“It is precisely Russian that is taught well.”
(Respondent 40, Belarusian- and Russian-language schools)

“The fact that it has to be studied.” *(Respondent 53, Russian-language school)*

English Language Proficiency and Learning

The fourth language addressed in the online questionnaire was **English**. Proficiency in English is potentially directly linked to the future educational and life trajectories of Belarusian children living in Lithuania. The survey showed that **75% of respondents (66 responses)** assess their children’s English proficiency as **basic or upper-basic** (23 responses) or lower – at the level of knowing only individual words or phrases (39 responses). Another **four respondents** indicated that their children do not know English at all.

Children of **12.5% of respondents (11 responses)** have an **intermediate level** of English proficiency. Another **12.5%** reported proficiency at a **native-like level (3 responses)** or **close to fluent (8 responses)**.

Figure 13. English language proficiency.

At the same time, the majority of respondents (**79%, 70 responses**) indicated that their children study English **systematically**, either at educational institutions or as a regular school subject. Another **11 respondents (12%)** reported that their children study English through **additional classes**, and only **9% (8 responses)** stated that their children do not study English at all.

Figure 14. Learning of the English language.

Overall, most parents are satisfied with the level of English language instruction. **61% (49 responses)** selected either “**rather satisfied**” or “**fully satisfied.**” Another **36% (29 respondents)** indicated that they were **uncertain**. Only **3%** clearly expressed dissatisfaction.

Figure 15. Satisfaction with English language Instruction.

Respondents left almost no comments regarding specific reasons for dissatisfaction. Among the few responses received, some mentioned the **insufficient number of English language instruction hours** in educational institutions.

Conclusions

The children of survey respondents are predominantly **Russian-speaking**. In total, **68.1%** of responses confirm that children use Russian predominantly in everyday life. Another **14.3%** use Russian regularly, though not as their primary language of communication. Between **15.4% and 22%** of respondents report that their children use Belarusian exclusively or predominantly, while **28.6%** state that their children use Belarusian regularly, though not most of the time. Regarding English, **75%** of respondents assess their children's proficiency as **basic or upper-basic, or lower**. Only **12.5%** report native-like or near-fluent proficiency. As for Lithuanian, **72.5%** of respondents indicate that their children have **basic, upper-basic, or lower levels** of proficiency, while only **11%** report fluent or near-fluent command of the language.

The largest proportion of children systematically study **Lithuanian: 86.6%** of respondents confirmed this. Similarly, **79%** reported systematic study of **English**. At the same time, **51%** stated that their children systematically study **Belarusian**, which exceeds the percentage of respondents whose children attend Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija (30.8%). This suggests that **parents actively seek ways for their children to learn Belarusian** even if they were unable to enroll them in the only Belarusian-language institution. **Russian** is studied systematically by the smallest share of children – **45%** of parents responded positively to this question.

Parental satisfaction varies by language. In the case of **Lithuanian**, only **48%** report being satisfied with the quality of instruction, while **24%** are clearly dissatisfied. For **Belarusian**, **61%** are fully or rather satisfied, and only **12%** express dissatisfaction. Satisfaction with the teaching of **Russian** stands at **62%**, with **10%** dissatisfied. Finally, **61%** of respondents are rather or fully satisfied with the teaching of **English**, and only **3%** clearly express dissatisfaction.

When discussing dissatisfaction with Lithuanian-language instruction, parents whose children attend Lithuanian-language institutions report **a lack of additional support** and note that they had to ensure their children's language development independently. The main group of respondents – whose children attend minority schools with Belarusian or Russian as the language of instruction – highlight **the absence of methodologies for teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language** and the lack of a systematic approach to integrating migrant children. They also point to insufficient opportunities for language practice, as well as issues related to teacher motivation and the limited number of Lithuanian-language classes.

Despite relatively high overall satisfaction with Belarusian-language instruction, this category generated the largest number of critical comments. Most of them came from parents whose children attend **Skorinos gimnazija**. Their concerns focus primarily on the extensive use of Russian by teachers in the educational process. At the same time, parents whose children attend other institutions note the lack of additional opportunities to study Belarusian.

Those whose children study Russian left only seven comments. Most expressed a critical attitude toward the necessity of studying Russian, including respondents whose children attend Russian-language institutions. The few comments concerning English-language instruction primarily referred to the insufficient number of instructional hours.

Overall, the issues that most concern parents relate to **the study of Lithuanian and Belarusian languages**.

2.4. Future Plans, Integration, and Barriers

The next block of questions focused on examining the **future plans of respondents and their families**, particularly regarding their prospects of **living in Lithuania and integrating into Lithuanian society**.

When asked whether they consider the possibility of continuing to live in Lithuania for at least the **next 3-5 years**, the majority responded positively: **59% (54 responses)** selected either **“5 (yes)”** or **“4 (rather yes)”**. Another **34% (31 responses)** indicated that they were **uncertain**. Only **six respondents (7%)** selected **“2 (rather no)”**, suggesting they were unlikely to consider this option. No respondents selected a definite **“no.”**

Thus, even under conditions of uncertainty that many Belarusians in Lithuania currently face, the majority still view **Lithuania as their place of residence in the near future**.

Figure 16. Plans Regarding Living in Lithuania Over the Next 3–5 Years

It was also decided to find out whether respondents were considering moving to another country in the coming years. The question was formulated as follows: **“Are you considering the possibility of moving to another country (not Belarus and not Lithuania) in the coming years?”**

27% (25 responses) indicated that they are considering such a possibility, while 21% (19 responses) said they are not. The majority have not yet made a decision.

Figure 17. Plans to move to another country in the coming years.

Thus, only about half of the respondents have clearly decided whether they are ready to consider the option of moving from Lithuania to another country. At the same time, the share of those who are definitely considering such a possibility roughly corresponds to the percentage of parents who do not plan to remain in the country in the coming years (according to the previous question – 21% and 20% respectively).

The remaining respondents are generally willing to stay in Lithuania, but some of them cannot guarantee that they will not begin to consider moving in the future. This will likely depend on how their further experience in the country develops.

At the same time, the overwhelming majority of those who answered the question about a specific country they would choose if they decided to move indicated **Poland**. This suggests that potential plans to relocate are more likely related to issues such as learning a new language, integration, and future prospects, rather than to a desire to move to a country with, for example, a higher standard of living or a different climate. Most of those who are ready to leave Lithuania would prefer to remain within the same region.

Figure 18. Possible destinations for relocation from Lithuania.

Respondents were also asked a separate question about whether they consider Lithuania a permanent place of residence for their children in the future. Notably, despite the fact that this question concerns a more distant perspective and the future of their children, a significant number of respondents answered positively: **42% (38 responses)** said “yes” or “rather yes.” A considerable number could not provide a definite answer – **33 respondents (36%)** chose the

intermediate option “3.” Another **15% (14 respondents)** selected “**2 (rather no)**.” Only **7%** gave a clearly negative answer.

Thus, the number of Belarusian parents who participated in the survey and seriously consider Lithuania as a place where their children may live in the long term is almost **twice as high** as the number of those who would prefer their children to live in another country. At the same time, it should be noted that the number of the latter again roughly corresponds to the share of respondents who do not consider Lithuania a place for their family to live in the near future and who express a clear desire to move (22%).

It is also understandable that many respondents find it difficult to make a definite decision, as well as that the share of those who clearly see Lithuania as their children’s permanent place of residence (42%) is somewhat lower than the share of those who plan to continue living in the country in the near future (59%). First, the current situation does not encourage long-term planning. Second, the answer to this question will undoubtedly depend on how successfully children integrate into Lithuanian society and whether they acquire sufficient proficiency in Lithuanian to continue their education and life in Lithuania.

Figure 19. Plans regarding Lithuania as a permanent place of residence for children.

In connection with the previous question, parents were also given the opportunity to describe their thoughts and plans in more detail by answering the open-ended question: “**How do you currently envision the further educational path of your children?**”

A variety of responses were received, which is understandable given the diverse situations in which families find themselves. An analysis of these comments allows for the following conclusions.

1. Continuing education in Lithuania.

The majority of respondents (59%) in one way or another plan to continue their children’s education in Lithuania in the short or medium term, either at their current level of education or at the next stage. At the same time, the level of certainty regarding this choice varies – from definite answers to mentions of this option as one of several possibilities.

The responses also differ depending on the language of instruction that families plan to choose. Some respondents intend for their children to study in Lithuania **in Lithuanian**, while others plan for them to study **in another language** within Lithuania. Naturally, the variability of the language of instruction is greater at the level of **secondary education** than when discussing **higher education**. In the latter case, some families plan for their children to study in Lithuania **in Lithuanian**, while others consider **English-language programs**.

At least **21 respondents (23%)** identified **Lithuanian** as the only language of instruction they are considering or as one of the possible options. Among them, **12 parents (13.2%)** indicated Lithuanian as the **only option**:

“It is difficult to say. For now, I see that they will continue studying in Lithuania in Lithuanian.” (Respondent 3, school and kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“University in Lithuanian.” (Respondent 12, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“The next stage is school. Education in Lithuanian.” (Respondent 20, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction, kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“We plan for the child to go to a Lithuanian-language school or gymnasium.”
(Respondent 22, kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)

“My daughter plans to enroll in a university in Lithuania, in Lithuanian.”
(Respondent 33, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“We want to transfer both daughters to Lithuanian-language institutions to ensure a higher level of education and better integration into the Lithuanian community.”
(Respondent 36, school and kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Apparently, after primary school the education will be in Lithuanian. We would prefer English, but it is expensive.” (Respondent 62, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Most likely the child will go to a Lithuanian school, because I have heard many negative reviews from parents about the Skorinos gymnasium (mainly that children there receive a weak level of Lithuanian, that much communication in the school takes place in Russian rather than Belarusian, and that the approach to education is Soviet-style, whereas we would prefer a modern one).”
(Respondent 86, kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

The remaining respondents mention **Lithuanian alongside other possible options**:

“Improve the level of Lithuanian and try to get into a Lithuanian gymnasium. It would be good to have the possibility for the child to study in Belarusian with a strong level of Lithuanian teaching.” (Respondent 4, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“We don’t know what would be better for the future: trying for a Lithuanian gymnasium or switching to English.” (Respondent 37, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“The older child – continuing education in school in English and then enrolling in a university with English as the language of instruction; the younger one – a Lithuanian school.”

(Respondent 39, school with English as the language of instruction, kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)

“School – we would like it to be in Lithuanian, Belarusian, and English.” (Respondent 43, kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“In Lithuania, in Lithuanian and English.”
(Respondent 71, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“They will study in higher education institutions in Lithuanian or English. At the moment, no other options are visible.”
(Respondent 89, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

The rest of the parents consider the possibility that their children will **continue their education in Lithuania but not in Lithuanian**, or they did not specify the language of instruction:

“Switching to education in English at school, and studying in English at university.”
(Respondent 6, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Continuing studies in a gymnasium and possibly also in a vocational school.”
(Respondent 8, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“An English-language university, possibly in another country.”
(Respondent 11, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“We would like a Belarusian school with strong Lithuanian and mandatory English, so that the child keeps the option of continuing studies at a university.”
(Respondent 24, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“We want English because we do not know how long we will live here, and Belarusian so that the child knows and loves their roots.”
(Respondent 56, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“We continue studying at Skorinos gymnasium and are preparing for admission to EHU.”
(Respondent 76, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“For now, the plan after the current school is to move to Karoliniškės Gymnasium in Vilnius (with instruction in Russian and compulsory Lithuanian) to obtain secondary education.”
(Respondent 77, kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)

“They will continue studying in Russian-language schools.”
(Respondent 82, school and kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)

2. Continuing education in another country

At least **14 respondents** are considering the possibility of their children pursuing education **outside Lithuania**. Some note that this is connected, among other reasons, with what they perceive as the difficulty of achieving a sufficiently high level of Lithuanian to pursue higher education in that language.

“In English – outside Lithuania.”

(Respondent 2, schools with Russian and English as the languages of instruction)

“They will finish gymnasium and apply to universities. One will definitely apply outside Lithuania and look for programs in English. The other has not yet decided.”

(Respondent 21, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“For now we will stay here, but the older child wants to pursue higher education either in Poland or in Ukraine.”

(Respondent 57, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“School, then university somewhere further West.”

(Respondent 28, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“We are preparing our children for European English-language universities. For now we are in Lithuania and plan to remain in the same school with instruction in English. Ideally, there would also be the language.”

(Respondent 72, schools with English and Lithuanian as the languages of instruction)

“Study English and go abroad for university after school. I do not believe the children will achieve a sufficient level of Lithuanian.”

(Respondent 75, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

The next question concerned **the importance of integration into Lithuanian society** from the parents’ perspective. The **absolute majority of respondents consider this necessary**.

80% answered this question clearly positively. **17%** found it difficult to give a definite answer. Only **3 respondents (3%)** do not consider integration important.

Thus, **even those parents who have clear plans to change their country of residence in the coming years still consider integration important**.

Figure 20. Attitudes toward the necessity of integration into Lithuanian society.

Naturally, Belarusian families face a number of difficulties on the path to integration into Lithuanian society. Based on respondents’ answers to the relevant question (where multiple options could be selected and respondents could add their own), it can be concluded that

insufficient proficiency in Lithuanian is the main challenge for most families: **70 respondents (77%)** identified the language barrier as one of the key obstacles.

Many respondents also reported **a lack of contacts with Lithuanians (49%)**, **lack of time or financial resources (45%)**, **insufficient information about integration opportunities (34%)**, and **difficulties finding employment in their professional field (34%)**.

Some respondents also mentioned **feeling like outsiders (30%)** and **negative attitudes toward them within Lithuanian society (18%)**. A smaller number of respondents pointed to **cultural differences that hinder integration (11%)**, while **14%** stated that they **do not have a desire to integrate**. Only **three respondents** indicated that they **do not encounter any difficulties**.

Figure 21. Difficulties on the path to integration into Lithuanian society.

At the same time, Belarusian families are taking concrete steps to accelerate their integration. According to responses to the relevant question (where multiple options could be selected and respondents could add their own), **the majority of respondents (71 responses, 78%) are learning Lithuanian**, and many are also **interested in Lithuanian culture and history (58 respondents, 64%)** and **attend Lithuanian cultural events (51 responses, 56%)**.

Thirty respondents indicated that they **have Lithuanian friends**, while **25** reported that their **children attend Lithuanian schools or kindergartens**. Some respondents also **work in Lithuanian-speaking professional environments** or **participate in Lithuanian civic, volunteer, or sports activities**. Only **12 respondents** stated that they **do not do anything in particular to facilitate integration**.

Figure 22. Steps toward integration.

Respondents were also asked separately what kind of assistance would be helpful for them or their children to better integrate in Lithuania. Based on the analysis of responses to this open-ended question, several broad categories can be identified.

1. Assistance with learning Lithuanian

At least **33 respondents (36.3%)** indicated that assistance with learning Lithuanian would be helpful for their integration into society. Respondents mentioned the need for **financial support, low-cost or free language courses** for both children and adults, and also proposed improving the **quality of Lithuanian language instruction for non-native speakers**.

“Lithuanian language courses for children.”

(Respondent 15, institution not specified, child aged 5)

“Language courses, especially if they were available at a symbolic price, because finances are important for us right now; also joint events with Lithuanians.”

(Respondent 19, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Language courses not aimed at passing the state exam but at actually mastering Lithuanian.” *(Respondent 20, school with Belarusian and kindergarten with Lithuanian as the languages of instruction)*

“Probably, first of all, help with the language.”

(Respondent 22, kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Good programs for learning Lithuanian.”

(Respondent 44, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Effective Lithuanian language teaching at an affordable price.”

(Respondent 70, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Changes to the Lithuanian language program in minority schools ...”

(Respondent 90, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

2. Lithuanian – Belarusian integration activities

The second most frequently mentioned category is the organization of **integration programs and activities for Belarusians**. At least **22 respondents (24.1%)** referred to this need.

Respondents especially emphasized the importance of **creating opportunities for interaction between Lithuanians and Belarusians**, both for **children and adults**. The purpose of such initiatives would not only be learning Lithuanian but also **getting to know each other's cultures and values** and improving relations between Belarusians living in Lithuania and the Lithuanian population.

Notably, this need was also expressed by parents whose children already attend **Lithuanian-language institutions**. This suggests that simply enrolling children in Lithuanian-language schools does not automatically guarantee successful integration.

“Joint Belarusian (Belarusian-language) - Lithuanian projects: camps, clubs, projects, etc.”
(Respondent 3, school and kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“Joint events/camps/sports and creative clubs with opportunities for integration; high-quality Lithuanian language teaching; initiatives for real, not just formal, integration of foreigners.” (Respondent 16, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Joint Belarusian-Lithuanian networking events. The children have integrated well, but my husband and I much less so. We created a Belarusian community in Klaipeda, but there is not enough time for integration into Lithuanian society.”

(Respondent 23, schools with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“... some cultural or professional meetings with Lithuanians. Otherwise we somehow live in parallel.” (Respondent 24, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“The opportunity to have more contacts and friendships with the local population.”
(Respondent 43, kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“Language courses + creating/promoting platforms for interaction with Lithuanians.”
(Respondent 67, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

3. Assistance with employment

Some respondents also mentioned the need for support with **retraining and employment**, both for themselves and, in the future, for their children (career guidance). These issues are closely connected with the question of **learning Lithuanian**.

“Help with learning Lithuanian and assistance with finding employment in one's professional field.” (Respondent 9, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Searching for work and education opportunities for one child with special needs.”
(Respondent 14, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Professional retraining.” (Respondent 48, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Help for children to learn the language, and help for parents to find employment.”
(Respondent 82, kindergarten and school with Russian as the language of instruction)

Respondents also raised issues related to **access to psychological support and loans, simplifying the legalization process for Belarusians, and calls for non-discrimination toward Belarusians at the state level.**

Conclusions

Thus, even under conditions of uncertainty, **the majority of respondents (59%) clearly consider Lithuania their place of residence in the near future.** The share of those who definitely consider moving to another country corresponds to the percentage of parents who do not plan to remain in Lithuania in the coming years (**21% and 20% respectively**). The remaining respondents are generally willing to stay in Lithuania, although some cannot guarantee that they will not begin to consider relocation in the future. This will likely depend on how their further experience of living in the country develops. The overwhelming majority of those who named a specific country they would consider moving to indicated **Poland**. This suggests that they would move to a country with a **similar standard of living and within the same region**. It can therefore be assumed that potential relocation plans are more closely related to issues such as **language learning, challenges of integration, and perceived future prospects.**

At the same time, **a significant number of parents (42%) seriously consider Lithuania as a permanent place of residence for their children, which is almost twice as high as the number of those who would prefer their children to live in another country.** It should be noted that the number of the latter again roughly corresponds to the share of respondents who do not consider Lithuania a place of residence for their family in the near future and who express a clear intention to move (**22%**). The relatively large number of respondents who are uncertain about this question, as well as the fact that the share of those who clearly see Lithuania as their children’s permanent place of residence (42%) is somewhat lower than the share of those who definitely plan to remain in the country in the near future (59%), is likely related to the fact that the **current situation does not encourage long-term planning.** In addition, the answer will undoubtedly depend on **how successfully children integrate into Lithuanian society and whether they achieve sufficient proficiency in Lithuanian.**

When discussing plans regarding their children’s education, **most respondents (59%) consider continuing education in Lithuania.** Some parents intend for their children to study in Lithuania **in Lithuanian**, while others consider **studying in Lithuania in another language.** Other parents are considering the possibility of their children **pursuing education abroad.** Some note that this is partly connected with what they perceive as the difficulty of achieving a sufficient level of Lithuanian to pursue **higher education in that language.**

The **absolute majority of respondents (80%),** including some of those who intend to move to another country, consider **integration into Lithuanian society necessary.** Many families are already taking concrete steps toward this goal. Most respondents (**78%**) are learning Lithuanian, are interested in Lithuanian culture and history (**64%**), and attend Lithuanian cultural events (**56%**). Many also have Lithuanian friends, and some of their children attend **Lithuanian educational institutions.**

At the same time, Belarusians face **certain challenges along this path.** For most respondents, the main difficulty is **insufficient proficiency in Lithuanian (77%).** Many also report **a lack of contact with Lithuanians (49%), lack of time or financial resources (45%), insufficient**

information about integration opportunities (34%), and difficulties finding employment in their professional field (34%). Some respondents also mentioned **feeling like outsiders (30%)** and **negative attitudes toward them from Lithuanian society (18%).**

These concerns are reflected in respondents' answers regarding the types of support needed for more successful integration. Families expressed the need for **assistance with learning Lithuanian**, such as accessible courses for both children and adults. Respondents also proposed **improving the quality of Lithuanian language instruction as a foreign language**. In addition, there is interest in **integration programs and initiatives**. Respondents emphasized the need for **interaction between Lithuanians and Belarusians**, which would help with language learning, provide opportunities to become familiar with each other's cultures and values, and improve relations between the two communities. This need is also expressed by parents whose children attend Lithuanian-language institutions. This suggests that **simply enrolling children in institutions where Lithuanian is the primary language of instruction does not automatically guarantee successful integration of families.**

2.5. Public Demand for Advocacy and Priority Areas of Action to Address Existing Challenges

Given the existing challenges, particularly in the field of education, it appears logical that the overwhelming majority of survey participants consider organized efforts to represent and defend the interests of Belarusian parents and children in Lithuania to be necessary. **95% of respondents consider this important or very important.**

Figure 23. The need for advocacy in the field of education.

An even larger share of respondents – **98%** - supports the idea of **institutionalization in order to represent and defend their interests.**

In response to a follow-up question, parents explained what, in their view, such an organization should do. First and foremost, it should **unite Belarusian families in Lithuania** and serve as a **channel of communication with the state**, representing their interests, especially given that **new migrants in Lithuania are not recognized as a national minority and therefore require additional mechanisms to protect their rights.**

According to respondents, the issues that such an organization should address include **formal and non-formal education**, including support for **children with special needs**, **preserving national identity**, and **expanding opportunities to study the Belarusian language and culture**. Other areas mentioned include **supporting integration into Lithuanian society**, **creating opportunities for interaction with the Lithuanian community**, **working with Belarusian teachers and assisting them in validating their qualifications**, as well as **organizing camps and other educational or community activities.**

Figure 24. Support for the creation of an Association of Belarusian Parents in Lithuania.

When discussing respondents' views on **integration into Lithuanian society and the preservation of their identity**, the overwhelming majority confirmed the conclusions that can be drawn from the information presented in the previous sections when answering the relevant questions in the final block.

In particular, **the vast majority of respondents consider it important for their children to learn Lithuanian for their future life in Lithuania. 86%** answered this question clearly positively, while **only two respondents** considered it rather unimportant.

Figure 25. Parents' attitudes toward their children learning Lithuanian.

Similarly, the majority of respondents consider it important for their children to learn **Belarusian** in order to preserve their identity. **Eighty-three survey participants (91%)** gave a clearly positive answer to this question. A small number of respondents were unable to determine their position, and only **one person** indicated that they do not consider this important.

Thus, despite the fact that, as noted above, **69% of respondents' children predominantly or exclusively use Russian**, almost all respondents want their children to **learn Belarusian** and consider this important for preserving their identity.

Figure 26. Parents' attitudes toward their children learning Belarusian to preserve their identity.

The overwhelming majority of respondents are also interested in **improving the quality of education and creating more favorable learning conditions for Belarusian children in Lithuanian educational institutions**, as well as **creating or expanding opportunities for children in Lithuania to study the Belarusian language, literature, and history**. In addition, respondents expressed interest in **various educational and cultural activities for Belarusian children and parents in Lithuania**.

Figure 27. Support for improving the quality of education and learning conditions.

Figure 28. Support for expanding the teaching of the Belarusian language and other subjects.

Figure 29. Interest in other educational and cultural activities.

Finally, Belarusian parents were invited to answer several open-ended questions in order to describe in greater detail the broader challenges and difficulties they face in Lithuania across different areas, as well as to identify key issues concerning Belarusian families in Lithuania that they would like to communicate to Lithuanian society and organizations.

An analysis of responses to the first of these questions shows that Belarusians are primarily concerned with the following groups of problems.

1. Problems related to the Belarusian language and identity

Most responses to this question relate to the **preservation of the Belarusian language and identity**. At least **34 respondents (37.4% of respondents)** mentioned these issues in their answers to the open-ended question. The discussion concerns both **formal and non-formal education**, expanding opportunities to study relevant subjects, and improving the opportunities that already exist, for example at **Skorinos gymnasium**.

“The possibility of studying in Belarusian.” (Respondent 4, school with Russian as the language of instruction; Respondent 9, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Expanding the number of classes with Belarusian as the language of instruction...”
(Respondent 17, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Preserving the Belarusian language. At the same time helping children learn Lithuanian at a level that allows them to participate in everyday life.”
(Respondent 18, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Studying Belarusian language, literature, and history at a sufficient level.”
(Respondent 21, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“The possibility of creating Belarusian-language classes in local schools. Or classes where Belarusian could be studied. Or an additional official institution for Belarusian children.”
(Respondent 24, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“For children: additional clubs for Belarusian language, Belarusian literature, the history of Belarus, and Belarusian art.”
(Respondent 26, kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“There is too little Belarusian in Skorinos gymnasium and a shortage of places and teachers. The entire class studies in English and Lithuanian, with no division into groups.”
(Respondent 40, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“The existence of real education in Belarusian – in practice, not only on paper.”
(Respondent 64, kindergarten with English as the language of instruction)

“Preserving the Skorinos gymnasium.”
(Respondent 66, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Another Belarusian-language school, although I understand that this is very difficult under the current conditions and attitudes toward national minorities.”
(Respondent 79, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

2. Problems related to the Lithuanian language and integration into Lithuanian society.

Another group of responses that can be identified separately concerns **addressing difficulties with learning Lithuanian and facilitating integration into Lithuanian society**. Some responses refer to the difficulty of integrating into Lithuanian-language educational institutions due to the **absence of a structured support system**. In addition, respondents believe it is necessary to address the **problem of Belarusian children being pushed into Russian-language schools**, as well as the **lack of an appropriate approach to teaching Lithuanian in minority schools**. Respondents also mention the **difficulties faced by students who moved to Lithuania in the upper grades when taking state examinations in Lithuanian**.

“The problem of Belarusian children being pushed into Russian-language schools, because there is no effective program for integrating foreigners into Lithuanian-language schools. While it is still somehow possible to cope in primary school through one’s own efforts, entering secondary school becomes almost impossible.”
(Respondent 3, school and kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

“Integration into Lithuanian society, improving the quality of education in national minority schools, and creating more opportunities for Belarusian children to study their language and culture.”

(Respondent 10, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“Additional Lithuanian language classes. Ideally, these would be activities for both children and parents at the same time in some gamified learning formats. Maybe summer camps. Perhaps city-based games like ‘Encounter’-type activities in Lithuanian during the summer – something simple and engaging.”

(Respondent 28, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Learning Lithuanian in diaspora schools does not allow for full integration into Lithuanian society; as a result, Lithuanian-speaking and Russian-speaking communities exist in parallel.” *(Respondent 36, school and kindergarten with Russian as the language of instruction)*

“The problem of passing the final school exam in Lithuanian.”

(Respondent 12, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“There are no proper accessible methodologies or methodological materials for teaching and learning Lithuanian.” *(Respondent 35, school with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)*

“Children are required to pass the state exam in Lithuanian, even though proper instruction in Lithuanian for non-native speakers is not organized. As a result, parents are forced to look for private tutors at considerable cost.”

(Respondent 62, school with Russian as the language of instruction)

“Learning Lithuanian and continuing education after Belarusian- or Russian-language schools. Obtaining a profession.”

(Respondent 80, school with Belarusian as the language of instruction)

“This concerns children in the upper grades – they were unable to complete their education because the exams are only in Lithuanian.”

(Respondent 84, kindergarten with Lithuanian as the language of instruction)

Other responses also referred to issues related to **the legalization of families in Lithuania, the lack of accessible information about rights and obligations, problems faced by parents of children with special needs, and difficulties in finding employment.**

Finally, respondents were asked to list any **topics or issues they would like to communicate to Lithuanian society and state institutions.** Among the responses, the following categories can be identified:

1. Stereotypes about Belarusians in Lithuania.

Most responses in this section focus on the need to improve Lithuanians’ attitudes toward Belarusians and to overcome stereotypes which, according to respondents, currently exist in Lithuanian society.

At least **37 respondents (40.6%) addressed these issues** in one way or another. They consider it important to communicate that Belarusians respect Lithuania and Lithuanians, do not pose a threat, wish to live in Lithuania while respecting its residents, and want to contribute positively to

Lithuanian society. Respondents also mention that Belarusians and Lithuanians share a long common history and have similar cultures. In addition, they highlight the importance of informing Lithuanians about the events in Belarus and the context in which Belarusians in Lithuania currently live.

“About the fact that we are here – that we are not enemies – that we are interesting and do many good things for Lithuania.” (Respondent 2)

“That Belarusians are respectful and grateful for the opportunity to stay here while waiting for the moment when they can return to their homeland.” (Respondent 15)

“About the need for reciprocal steps toward the integration of Belarusians, about the constant tension and uncertainty in which Belarusians in Lithuania live, about cases of discrimination against Belarusians based on language, citizenship, former employment, etc.” (Respondent 16)

“About the absence of any threat to Lithuania’s security from nationally oriented Belarusians.” (Respondent 17)

“Belarusians are not enemies but a nation that has lived side by side with Lithuanians for centuries, exchanging knowledge and cultural traditions. A nation that shared centuries of common history with Lithuanians.” (Respondent 25)

“About how our children try to learn Lithuanian, about Lithuanian-Belarusian events, about the fact that many Belarusians here are essentially refugees who face prison at home, and about how important it is for Belarusians to teach their children their native language.” (Respondent 41)

“That Belarusians are interested in integrating into the local environment. That Belarusians want to go home, not to ‘take over Vilnius.’” (Respondent 47)

“About the attitude of Belarusians in Lithuania toward culture and language – Belarusians have a very positive attitude toward Lithuanians and Lithuanian culture.” (Respondent 49)

“That Belarusians are not Russians.” (Respondents 57, 66)

“About the political situation in the country, the reasons for emigration, the difficulties faced by parents and children, the need to develop and implement integration programs, effective methodologies for teaching Lithuanian, and the need for support and understanding.” (Respondent 70)

“1) It is very important to explain to Lithuanians why many Belarusians speak Russian. 2) That Belarus was also part of the Grand Duchy of Lithuania and that the history of the GDL is an important part of Belarusian history.” (Respondent 86)

“Belarusians are a valuable resource that Lithuania currently has. They should be helped to integrate and build friendly relationships.” (Respondent 89)

2. Lithuanian language and integration into Lithuanian society.

Another 21 respondents (23%) addressed issues related to learning the Lithuanian language and integrating into society. Respondents pointed to the need for additional support and reciprocal steps from Lithuanian society if it is interested in the faster integration of Belarusian children and their parents. This includes additional accessible opportunities to learn Lithuanian, including within Lithuanian-language schools, as well as integration-focused activities.

“We support our children learning Lithuanian, but there is no real support, courses, additional classes, or integration programs. We have to manage on our own, while Lithuanian schools are not very willing to admit foreigners without knowledge of the language.” (Respondent 3)

“First and foremost – given the lack of time and financial resources – learning Lithuanian. State support is needed.” (Respondent 20)

“Lithuanian should be taught as a foreign language for migrants. Unfortunately, this depends on the teachers. In most cases it is taught in the same way as for local children. The same applies to literature.” (Respondent 21)

“About our holidays. Children write projects – perhaps there could be joint competitions for children. Common Olympiads where children could meet Lithuanians and interact.” (Respondent 67)

“Even children who were born in Lithuania do not speak Lithuanian at home, so they need additional classes.” (Respondent 78)

“There are no integration or vocational education programs in Russian/Belarusian. School graduation exams are also an issue. I believe Belarusians should have different conditions compared to Lithuanians.” (Respondent 80)

“Additional Lithuanian language classes should be introduced in Lithuanian-language schools.” (Respondent 88)

3. Belarusian language and identity

Fifteen respondents (16.5%) emphasized the importance of communicating information about the Belarusian language and culture to Lithuanian society. Respondents stress the need to explain the importance of preserving Belarusian identity, to highlight the need for support in organizing Belarusian-language education in Lithuania, and to clarify that this does not pose a threat to Lithuanian society but, on the contrary, contributes to its security.

“About the fact that we want to preserve our culture and that this in no way threatens Lithuanian society.” (Respondent 24)

“Belarusians send their children to Russian schools because there is no other option. One solution could be to open Belarusian classes in Lithuanian schools. It would also help to simplify requirements for teachers from Belarus and Ukraine so they can work in Lithuanian schools in their native languages.” (Respondent 39)

“If there is a desire to reduce the influence of the ‘Russian world,’ it would make sense to support the study of the Belarusian language.” (Respondent 40)

“The need to create conditions for preserving and promoting the Belarusian language and cultural traditions among Belarusians.” (Respondent 43)

“That Belarusians have the right to study in the Belarusian language.” (Respondent 64)

4. Legal issues

Another seven respondents raised specific legal issues and challenges faced by Belarusians in Lithuania. These include the inability to renew passports outside Belarus, as well as the lack of certain social guarantees for children with special needs who reside in Lithuania on temporary residence permits.

“About the very difficult situation of those who suddenly lose their residence permits while being unable to return to Belarus, as well as the problem of passports expiring and the impossibility of renewing them.” (Respondent 12)

“To defend the interests of Belarusians when laws on movement are tightened, particularly regarding the number of visits to Belarus per year.” (Respondent 34)

“People moved to Lithuania with children with special needs and receive almost no support because they only have temporary residence status (no access to pensions or benefits), which creates many difficulties and stress.” (Respondent 56)

“About the lack of motivation to integrate when it is impossible to obtain a passport.” (Respondent 72)

“Problems with passports and the inability to return.” (Respondent 91)

Conclusions

Thus, the overwhelming majority of survey participants (**95%**) consider organized advocacy to represent and defend the interests of Belarusian parents and children in the field of education to be necessary. Even more respondents (**98%**) support the idea of institutionalizing such representation and advocacy. They expect such an organization to **unite Belarusian families in Lithuania and serve as a channel of communication with the state** in order to represent their interests – especially given that recent Belarusian migrants in Lithuania **are not recognized as a national minority and therefore require additional measures to protect their rights**. This concerns education, the preservation of national identity, integration into Lithuanian society, and related issues.

The relevance of these topics for respondents is further confirmed by answers to additional questions. A majority of respondents (**86%**) believe it is important that their children **learn Lithuanian for their future life in Lithuania**. An even larger share of parents (**91%**) consider it important that their children **learn the Belarusian language in order to preserve their national identity**. This is particularly notable given that, as shown earlier, most of the respondents’ children **predominantly use Russian in everyday communication**. Most respondents are also interested in **improving the quality of education and creating more favorable learning conditions for Belarusian children in Lithuania**, expanding opportunities to study the

Belarusian language, literature, and related subjects, as well as organizing additional educational and cultural activities for Belarusian children and parents.

When reflecting on the main challenges faced by Belarusian families in Lithuania at a broader level, the largest share of respondents (**37.4%**) mentioned **difficulties related to preserving the Belarusian language and identity**. These concerns largely relate to education – **expanding opportunities to study Belarusian and related subjects**, as well as improving the opportunities that already exist. For example, some parents expressed concern about **the use of Russian in the educational process at the Skorinos gymnasium**.

Respondents also mentioned **problems related to learning Lithuanian and the lack of support mechanisms for integration into Lithuanian society**. These include difficulties integrating into Lithuanian-language institutions due to the absence of structured support programs. Parents also raised concerns about **Belarusian children being pushed toward Russian-language institutions** and about the lack of appropriate approaches to **teaching Lithuanian as a second or foreign language in minority schools**. Other responses referred to issues related to **the legal status of families in Lithuania, insufficient information about rights and obligations, challenges faced by children with special needs, and difficulties in finding employment**.

Finally, when identifying the issues that should be communicated to Lithuanian society and institutions, most respondents (**40.7%**) emphasized **the need to improve Lithuanian attitudes toward Belarusians and to overcome existing stereotypes**. They believe it is important to highlight that **Belarusians respect Lithuania and Lithuanians, do not pose a threat, and wish to contribute positively to Lithuanian society**, with which they share a long history and cultural similarities. Respondents also noted the importance of **informing Lithuanians about the situation in Belarus and the difficult circumstances in which many Belarusians in Lithuania currently live**.

Another **23% of responses** concerned **learning Lithuanian and integration into society**. Families emphasize the need for **additional support and proactive steps from Lithuanian institutions and society** if the goal is the successful and rapid integration of Belarusian children and parents. This includes **more accessible opportunities to learn Lithuanian**, including additional support within Lithuanian-language schools, as well as **integration-focused programs and activities**.

In addition, **16.5% of parents** stressed the importance of explaining to Lithuanian society why **preserving Belarusian identity – through opportunities to study in the Belarusian language in Lithuania – is important and beneficial**. According to respondents, this **does not threaten Lithuanian society but rather contributes to its social cohesion and security**.

Other comments referred to **legal and administrative challenges**, including **the inability to renew Belarusian passports abroad** and the **lack of social guarantees for children with special needs who reside in Lithuania under temporary residence permits**.

Conclusion

This study is based on a survey conducted in the summer of 2025 and takes place at a critical moment when the Belarusian family community in Lithuania is transitioning from individual adaptation to institutionalized civic activity. This makes the analysis of its needs and priorities particularly relevant. While the findings cannot be extrapolated to the entire Belarusian population in Lithuania, they make it possible to document **the challenges faced by the “active core” of Belarusian migrant families**, identify advocacy needs, and outline priorities for support.

Over the past five years, **a new social context has emerged in Lithuania**, shaped by a significant increase in the number of Belarusian citizens in the country. The current wave of migration is characterized by **a substantial proportion of families who have relocated with children**. Most of them are concentrated in Vilnius and the Vilnius district, which places additional pressure on the capital's educational and social infrastructure. As a result, many of the challenges related to access to education and integration services are **geographically concentrated in the capital**.

Belarusian families face challenges typical of migrant communities but also encounter a number of specific issues. For many parents, a key concern is a dual objective: **preserving Belarusian national identity while simultaneously integrating into Lithuanian society**.

Despite the clear demand for Belarusian-language education, **the existing education system is unable to meet this demand**. The only Belarusian-language institution in the country, Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija, is operating at the limit of its designed capacity. This has resulted in numerous rejections of applicants and led to the closure of the Belarusian-language kindergarten attached to the gymnasium in 2025. At the same time, **Lithuanian-language institutions are not always prepared to effectively integrate large numbers of migrant children**, and a systematic approach to teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language is largely absent. Under these conditions, a significant number of children end up enrolling in Russian-language institutions. Some parents describe this choice as forced and express dissatisfaction with the situation.

Most Belarusian families are currently in **a stage of active establishment and adaptation**. The majority reside in Lithuania on the basis of temporary residence permits, which can create a sense of uncertainty and generate a demand for legal support and advocacy, particularly in matters related to legalization and social guarantees. The relatively even distribution of children across age groups indicates that **the demand for educational and related services is comprehensive**.

The study covered 151 children of respondents, 137 of whom attend at least 41 educational institutions in Lithuania, almost all of them located in Vilnius. Most children receive education in Russian, including a significant number at the preschool level. Belarusian is the second most common language of instruction, represented primarily by Vilniaus Pranciškaus Skorinos gimnazija, the only institution of its kind in Lithuania. The third largest group studies in Lithuanian. This distribution demonstrates the Belarusian community's significant reliance on the Russian-language educational sector, despite parents' clear interest in enrolling their children in Lithuanian-language preschools.

Overall, parents' evaluation of educational institutions is relatively positive. However, respondents also identify several problems. More than half of parents (51.6%) express **dissatisfaction with the complete absence of Belarusian** in the educational process or with

the **insufficient quality of its instruction**. At the same time, 31.8% are dissatisfied with **the level of Lithuanian language instruction**, and 22% report **a lack of support for migrant children**. This suggests that parents experience insufficient support both for preserving Belarusian identity and for successful integration into the Lithuanian-language environment.

Approximately one-third of respondents (30.8%) are willing to consider transferring their children to another educational institution. This intention is most pronounced among parents whose children attend Russian-language schools and kindergartens. At the same time, **none of the 91 respondents identified Russian as their preferred educational alternative**: parents instead favor Belarusian or Lithuanian. This indicates **a clear aspiration for integration into Lithuanian society alongside a desire to preserve Belarusian identity**.

Among the main challenges in the educational sphere are **difficulties in learning Lithuanian** (28.6%), primarily due to the absence of a system for teaching it as a non-native language and the insufficient number of lessons. Respondents also point to the education system's **lack of preparedness to work with migrant children**. Additionally, 16.5% report **problems accessing Belarusian-language education** or difficulties in learning the language. Responses mention the shortage of Belarusian-language institutions, the inability to enroll in the Skorinos gymnasium, and the recent closure of the only Belarusian-language kindergarten in Vilnius.

Other challenges include the shortage of textbooks, insufficient attention to children with special educational needs, low motivation or qualifications among some teachers, an overloaded school curriculum, and instances of bullying. In response, parents highlight the need for additional educational support. Specifically, **30.8% of respondents report needing assistance in learning Lithuanian**. They suggest improving methodologies for teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language, introducing systematic instruction “from zero,” including for teenagers, and organizing additional lessons with native speakers. Parents also express demand for programs that support integration into Lithuanian-language educational environments, including integration clubs, tutoring support, and integration strategies at the municipal level.

The children of respondents are predominantly Russian-speaking: 68.1% of parents report that their children primarily use Russian in daily life. However, only 45% study Russian systematically. Children who primarily or exclusively use Belarusian represent between 15.4% and 22% of respondents' families, yet 51% of children study Belarusian systematically – approximately 20% more than the number of students enrolled in the Skorinos gymnasium. This indicates that **parents actively seek additional opportunities for their children to learn Belarusian**.

The level of English proficiency among children is assessed by 75% of respondents as “basic or pre-intermediate” or lower. A similar situation exists with Lithuanian: 72.5% of parents rate their children's Lithuanian proficiency as basic or lower, despite the fact that most children study these languages systematically (79% and 86.6%, respectively).

Parents are least satisfied with the quality of Lithuanian language instruction. Only 48% of respondents evaluate it positively, while 24% express clear dissatisfaction. Parents whose children attend Lithuanian-language schools note **the lack of additional support**, while those whose children study in minority-language schools highlight **the absence of methodologies for teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language** and **the lack of a systematic approach to integrating migrant children**.

Regarding Belarusian, 61% of respondents report being fully or somewhat satisfied with the quality of instruction, while 12% express dissatisfaction. Most critical comments come from parents of students at the Skorinos gymnasium and relate to **the occasional use of Russian by teachers** during the educational process. Meanwhile, parents of children attending other institutions point to **the lack of opportunities to study Belarusian**.

Approximately 62% of respondents are satisfied with Russian language instruction, while 10% are dissatisfied. However, comments reveal that some parents question the necessity of studying Russian. As for English, 61% of respondents are satisfied with its instruction, and only 3% express dissatisfaction, mostly related to the limited number of teaching hours.

Despite existing uncertainty, **most respondents (59%) consider Lithuania to be their place of residence in the near future**. The share of those considering relocation corresponds to the share of parents who do not plan to remain in Lithuania in the coming years (21% and 20%, respectively). Among those who specified a possible destination country, the majority indicated Poland.

A significant number of parents (42%) also consider **Lithuania as a potential permanent place of residence for their children** – nearly twice as many as those who would prefer their children to live in another country. The high proportion of undecided responses likely reflects the fact that **final decisions will depend on the success of integration** and the ability to achieve sufficient proficiency in Lithuanian.

A majority of parents (59%) view Lithuania as their place of residence in the coming years. A significant share (42%) also considers Lithuania as a potential long-term place of residence for their children. However, many families indicate that **their decisions will depend on the ability to achieve sufficient proficiency in Lithuanian**.

Most respondents (59%) consider **the possibility of their children pursuing further education in Lithuania**. Some parents plan for education in Lithuanian, while others consider education in other languages. Other families are considering educational opportunities abroad, partly due to doubts about their children's ability to achieve sufficient Lithuanian proficiency

The overwhelming majority of respondents (80%) believe integration into Lithuanian society is necessary and are already taking concrete steps in that direction. For example, 78% are learning Lithuanian, 64% are interested in Lithuanian culture and history, and 56% attend Lithuanian cultural events. Many respondents report having Lithuanian friends or sending their children to Lithuanian educational institutions.

At the same time, Belarusians face **a number of challenges in the process of integration**. The most common barrier is **insufficient proficiency in Lithuanian (77%)**. Respondents also mention a lack of contact with Lithuanians (49%), limited financial or time resources (45%), insufficient information about integration opportunities (34%), and difficulties finding employment in their professional field (34%). Some respondents report feelings of being outsiders (30%) and negative attitudes from parts of Lithuanian society (18%).

Accordingly, families emphasize **the need for support in learning Lithuanian**, including accessible language courses, improvements in the quality of teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language, and the development of integration programs. Respondents also highlight **the importance of expanding interactions between Belarusians and Lithuanians**, which could facilitate language learning and mutual understanding of cultures.

When asked about **the issues that should be communicated to Lithuanian society** and institutions, 40.7% of respondents emphasized the need to **improve attitudes toward Belarusians and overcome stereotypes**. They consider it important to highlight that Belarusians respect Lithuania and Lithuanians, do not pose a threat, and seek to contribute positively to Lithuanian society, with which they share historical ties and cultural similarities. Respondents also stress the importance of informing Lithuanian society about developments in Belarus and the difficult circumstances faced by Belarusians currently living in Lithuania.

In this context, it is notable that an overwhelming majority of survey participants (95%) believe organized efforts to represent and defend the interests of Belarusian parents and children in the field of education are necessary. An even larger proportion (98%) supports the institutionalization of such activities. Respondents expect that an organization of this kind would unite Belarusian families in Lithuania and serve as a communication channel with state institutions.

Most respondents (86%) believe **it is important for their children to learn Lithuanian** in order to live in Lithuania. An even larger share (91%) **considers it important for their children to learn Belarusian** in order to preserve national identity. The majority of respondents also express interest in improving the quality of education, expanding opportunities to learn Belarusian language and literature, and organizing additional educational and cultural activities for Belarusian children and parents.

Overall, the study demonstrates that the active segment of the Belarusian family community in Lithuania – primarily in Vilnius – is **oriented toward long-term integration and is ready for constructive dialogue**. Successfully integrating this group of migrants **will require a systematic response from public policy**, including the development of **effective approaches to teaching Lithuanian** as a foreign language, **stronger support for the integration** of migrant children into the education system, and expanded **opportunities to preserve Belarusian language and identity**. Cooperation between public institutions and civil society organizations will also play an important role in this process.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the challenges identified in the study and the needs expressed by parents, the following recommendations are proposed for key stakeholders. The recommendations are also formulated in light of **Resolution No. 2499 (2023) of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe**, which recognizes the unique and prolonged nature of the exile of hundreds of thousands of Belarusians who were forced to leave the country due to repression. The resolution emphasizes the responsibility of Council of Europe member states to ensure dignified living conditions, full realization of fundamental rights, and sustainable integration for Belarusians in exile until conditions allow their return to a democratic Belarus.

Particular emphasis is placed on supporting children and families in the areas of education, linguistic and cultural integration, as well as on preserving and developing the Belarusian language and identity through educational and cultural instruments, including in cases where communities do not hold the formal status of a national minority. This approach underscores the need for systemic measures by national authorities, municipalities, and civil society in Lithuania. In this context, support for the education and integration of Belarusians in exile should be viewed not merely as a temporary humanitarian response but as a contribution to the protection of human rights, social cohesion, and the future democratic transformation of the region.

I. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR NATIONAL AUTHORITIES

1. Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of Lithuania (Švietimo, mokslo ir sporto ministerija)

It is recommended to:

1) Develop and implement a national model for teaching Lithuanian as a non-native language

Such a model should include:

- clearly defined proficiency levels (A1–B2);
- age-appropriate curricula, including tailored programs for adolescents;
- dedicated teaching hours within school curricula rather than incorporating Lithuanian as a non-native language into general language classes.

2) Provide methodological and financial support to schools enrolling migrant children:

This may include:

- funding for additional Lithuanian language instruction hours;
- the introduction of tutor or teaching assistant positions;
- access to psychological and social support services for students and families.

3) Reassess current approaches to minority-language education in light of new migration realities:

This review should address:

- the de facto channeling of Belarusian children into the Russian-language education sector;

- the lack of educational alternatives between Russian-language institutions and the single Belarusian-language gymnasium.

4) Invest in teacher training and professional development in the areas of:

- teaching Lithuanian as a foreign language;
- intercultural competence;
- working with migrant children and children with experience of forced migration.

5) Encourage the development of bilingual or transitional integration programs

Such programs could support the gradual transition of migrant children entering Lithuanian-language schools while ensuring adequate language support during the integration process.

6) Develop pathways for migrant teachers to contribute to the education system

Qualified teachers among Belarusian migrants represent an underutilized professional resource. Policies could include:

- simplified or accelerated procedures for recognition of foreign teaching diplomas;
- bridging programs focused on pedagogical Lithuanian and the Lithuanian curriculum;
- opportunities to work in schools as tutors, teaching assistants, or trainee teachers during the qualification recognition process.

Such measures could simultaneously strengthen staffing capacity in schools, support migrant pupils' integration, and facilitate professional integration of migrant educators.

2. Ministry of Social Security and Labour (Socialinės apsaugos ir darbo ministerija)

It is recommended to:

1) Develop targeted integration programs for migrant families with children

These may include:

- accessible information services;
- counseling on social and educational issues;
- parenting support programs.

2) Ensure sustainable funding for integration services

This could be achieved through long-term partnerships with municipalities and civil society organizations.

3) Develop family integration support centers or “one-stop” advisory services

Such services could provide coordinated access to education, social support, and legal information for migrant families.

3. Ministry of Culture and the Department of National Minorities (Kultūros ministerija and Tautinių mažumų departamentas)

It is recommended to:

1) Recognize the specific nature of the Belarusian community as a new migrant group

Although not formally recognized as a traditional national minority, the Belarusian new migrant community demonstrates a clear demand for preserving its language and cultural identity.

2) Support initiatives aimed at preserving Belarusian language and culture

Such support may include:

- extracurricular educational and cultural programs in the Belarusian language;
- the development and publication of educational materials;
- cultural initiatives targeting children and parents.

3) Support community-based cultural and educational initiatives

These initiatives should encourage dialogue and cooperation between Lithuanian and Belarusian communities.

**II. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR MUNICIPAL AUTHORITIES
(with particular attention to the City of Vilnius)**

1. Municipality of the City of Vilnius

It is recommended to::

1) Develop a local strategy for the integration of migrant children into the Vilnius education system.

Such a strategy should reflect the concentration of Belarusian families in the capital and coordinate education, language learning, and integration services.

2) Expand practical integration measures in educational institutions

These may include:

- additional free Lithuanian language classes in schools and kindergartens;
- pilot programs introducing tutors in Lithuanian-language institutions;
- integration clubs and extracurricular activities promoting interaction between Lithuanian and migrant children.

3) Implement pilot educational programs combining integration and identity support

Municipal authorities could support **pilot programs in selected Lithuanian-language schools** that combine:

- Lithuanian-language instruction as the primary language of education;
- optional modules in Belarusian language, literature, and culture;
- structured integration support through tutors and language mentors.

Such pilots could:

- reduce pressure on the Belarusian-language gymnasium;

- prevent forced transitions into Russian-language schools;
- support bilingual competence and cultural inclusion.

If successful, the model could later be expanded or adapted for other migrant communities.

4) Improve access to preschool education

This includes:

- identifying solutions following the closure of the Belarusian-language kindergarten;
- developing alternative mechanisms to support Belarusian-language environments for children.

5) Establish municipal coordination mechanisms for migrant integration

Such mechanisms could connect schools, municipal services, and civil society organizations working with migrant families.

III. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

1. Schools and Kindergartens

It is recommended to:

1) Introduce internal policies supporting migrant children:

These policies may include:

- individualized integration plans;
- regular communication and cooperation with parents.

2) Establish clear language policies within the educational environment

These policies should aim to:

- ensure consistent use of the official language of instruction;
- minimize informal reliance on Russian as a default communication language in schools.

3) Introduce peer integration initiatives

Examples include student mentorship programs pairing Lithuanian and migrant students to support language learning and social integration.

4) Engage migrant educators and community expertise

Schools may benefit from involving qualified migrant teachers or cultural mediators as tutors, assistants, or mentors who can support communication with families and assist students during language adaptation.

IV. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS

1. Lithuanian and Belarusian NGOs

It is recommended to:

1) Develop joint educational and integration programs

These may include:

- Lithuanian language courses;
- language practice clubs;
- cultural exchange initiatives.

2) Act as partners to public institutions

Civil society organizations can contribute to:

- implementing integration programs;
- monitoring the needs of migrant families;
- advocating for systemic policy improvements.

3) Facilitate community dialogue platforms

These platforms can strengthen cooperation and understanding between Lithuanian and Belarusian families.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PUBLIC COMMUNICATION AND DIALOGUE

1. Public Institutions and Media

It is recommended to:

1) Support public communication initiatives aimed at:

- reducing stereotypes about Belarusians;
- presenting Belarusians as constructive partners in integration.

2) Provide Lithuanian society with balanced information about:

- the situation in Belarus;
- the motivations of Belarusian families to integrate and contribute to Lithuanian society.

3) Encourage balanced media coverage

This should highlight the social, cultural, and economic contributions of Belarusian migrants.

Implementing these recommendations would contribute to the development of a more effective integration framework for migrant families in Lithuania while simultaneously supporting the preservation of linguistic and cultural diversity. In the case of Belarusian families in exile, such policies would address immediate integration challenges while also contributing to broader European commitments to protecting human rights, strengthening social cohesion, and supporting democratic transformation in the region.

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Annex 1. Questions Included in the Online Survey

1. How long have you been living in Lithuania on a permanent and uninterrupted basis?
2. In which city in Lithuania do you currently reside on a permanent basis? (Select an option or write your own in the last field.)
3. On what legal basis are you currently residing in Lithuania? (Select an option or write your own in the last field.)
4. Do you hold Belarusian citizenship? (Select an option or write your own in the last field.)
5. Do you have any other citizenship(s)? (Write “no” or list them.)
6. How many minor children (under 18) do you have? (Select an option or write your own in the last field.)
7. Please indicate the ages of your children (full years), separated by commas (e.g., 7, 15, 19).
8. Are your children being raised in a two-parent family (with both parents)? (Select an option or write your own in the last field.)
9. For how many years have your children been living in Lithuania on a permanent and uninterrupted basis? (If you have more than one child and the lengths of stay differ, indicate them separated by commas.)
10. In which city in Lithuania do your children currently reside? (Select an option or write your own in the last field.)
11. Do your children hold Belarusian citizenship? (Select an option or write your own in the last field; if your children have different citizenships, please explain.)
12. Do your children have any other citizenship(s)? (Write “no” or list them.)
13. Child 1: Please indicate, separated by commas, the following information: name of the educational institution, language of instruction, grade/group/club, and how long the child has attended this institution.
14. Child 2: Please indicate, separated by commas, the following information: name of the educational institution, language of instruction, grade/group/club, and how long the child has attended this institution.
15. Child 3: Please indicate, separated by commas, the following information: name of the educational institution, language of instruction, grade/group/club, and how long the child has attended this institution.
16. Child 4: Please indicate, separated by commas, the following information: name of the educational institution, language of instruction, grade/group/club, and how long the child has attended this institution. (If you do not have a fourth child, write “none.”)

17. Overall, are you satisfied with the educational institution(s) your children currently attend? (On a scale from 1 to 5.)
18. If you are not satisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with? (You may select several options or write your own in the last field.)
19. Would you like your child(ren) to study at a different educational institution in Lithuania? (On a scale from 1 to 5.)
20. If yes, which educational institution in Lithuania would you like your child(ren) to attend? (Please indicate the exact name or type of institution and the language of instruction.) What prevents them from studying there now?
21. Would you like your child(ren) to study in a different language than they do now?
22. If yes, in which language would you like your child(ren) to study?
23. Do your children study the Belarusian language in a systematic way (at an educational institution, in clubs, with tutors, etc.)?
24. If your children study Belarusian, are you satisfied with the quality of instruction? (On a scale from 1 to 5.)
25. If you are not satisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with?
26. Do your children speak Belarusian in everyday life (in the family, with friends, etc.)? (If you have several children and the answers differ, please explain in the last field.)
27. Do your children study Lithuanian?
28. If yes, are you satisfied with the quality of Lithuanian language instruction?
29. If you are not satisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with?
30. Do your children speak Lithuanian?
31. Do your children study Russian?
32. If yes, are you satisfied with the quality of Russian language instruction?
33. If you are not satisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with?
34. Do your children speak Russian?
35. Do your children study English?
36. If yes, are you satisfied with the quality of English language instruction?
37. If you are not satisfied, what exactly are you dissatisfied with?
38. Do your children speak English?

39. What problems related to your children's education have you encountered or are you currently encountering in Lithuania? (Please briefly describe them in your own words.)
40. What support would be useful to help address the problems your children face in the field of education in Lithuania?
41. How do you currently envision your children's further educational path? (Please briefly share your thoughts: where they will study at the next level of education, what they will study, and in which language.)
42. Do you consider the possibility of continuing to live in Lithuania over the next 3–5 years?
43. Do you see Lithuania as a possible permanent place of residence for your children in the future?
44. Do you consider the possibility of moving to another country (not Belarus and not Lithuania) in the coming years?
45. If yes, which country or countries are you considering first of all?
46. Do you consider it important to integrate into Lithuanian society?
47. What have you already done, or what are you doing, to integrate into Lithuanian society? (You may select several options or propose your own in the last field.)
48. What difficulties do you face on the path to integration? (You may select several options or propose your own in the last field.)
49. What support would be useful for you and/or your children for better integration in Lithuania?
50. Are you interested in improving the quality of education and creating more favorable learning conditions for Belarusian children in educational institutions in Lithuania?
51. Are you interested in creating or expanding opportunities for children in Lithuania to study the Belarusian language, literature, and history (for example, clubs, Sunday schools, optional classes)?
52. Are you interested in other educational and cultural activities for Belarusian children and parents in Lithuania?
53. How important do you consider the study of the Belarusian language for preserving your children's national identity?
54. How important do you consider the study of the Lithuanian language for your children's successful future life in Lithuania?
55. Do you consider organized efforts to represent and defend the interests of Belarusian parents and children in the field of education before Lithuanian institutions (advocacy) to be necessary?

56. In your opinion, which specific problems and issues faced by Belarusian parents and children in Lithuania require priority action?
57. What specifically do you consider important to communicate to Lithuanian society and state institutions (in connection with the life of Belarusians in Lithuania and their needs)?
58. Do you support the creation of an association of Belarusian parents in Lithuania?
59. In your opinion, what else should such an association do?
60. At the moment, we are considering various options for expanding Belarusian-language education in Lithuania. We are currently discussing the possibility of creating Belarusian classes in a private educational institution in Vilnius (instruction in Belarusian with a gradual transition to Lithuanian, free education, Lithuanian curriculum, and a state-recognized secondary education diploma). Would you be interested in such an educational opportunity for your children?
61. You may voluntarily leave your email address if you would like us to contact you in the future and invite you to join the association. Providing an email address is not mandatory and will in no way affect your participation in the survey.
62. Please use this field to provide any additional information or to ask questions.